

ExtremeXP

**Experiment Driven and user Experience Oriented Analytics for
Extremely Precise Outcomes and Decisions**

**D5.1: Core framework services – Monitoring,
Planning, Scheduling**

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Abstract	This deliverable documents the final version of the core ExtremeXP framework services responsible for designing, configuring, executing, and monitoring experiments and corresponding workflows. Moreover, it describes the final version of the data authorization mechanism supporting the ExtremeXP framework, as well as the secure and distributed management of datasets and knowledge pertaining to experimentation. The deliverable is organized around the software modules, services, and libraries that provide the above functionalities. It documents their internal structure and implementation, provides usage Information, and includes links to the corresponding repositories and online material. This deliverable provides an update over the contents of the previous deliverable of work package 5, i.e., D5.2.
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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
API	Application Programming Interface
DAL	Data Abstraction Layer
DDM	Decentralized Data Management
DID	Decentralized Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DMS	Design Model Storage
DSL	Domain-Specific Language
EVM	Ethereum Virtual Machine
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
JWT	JSON Web Token
LFDT	Linux Foundation's Decentralized Trust
LLM	Large Language Model
LSP	Language Server Protocol
PAP	Policy Administration Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PoA	Proof of Authority
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
SDK	Software Development Kit

Executive Summary

This deliverable documents the final version of the core ExtremeXP framework services responsible for designing, configuring, executing, and monitoring experiments and corresponding workflows. Moreover, it describes the final version of the data authorization mechanism supporting the ExtremeXP framework, as well as the secure and distributed management of datasets and knowledge pertaining to experimentation. It is organized around the software modules, services, and libraries that provide the above functionalities. It documents their internal structure and implementation, provides usage information, and includes links to the corresponding repositories and online material. This deliverable provides an update over the contents of the previous deliverable of work package 5, i.e., D5.2.

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives

The objective of WP5 is to develop and deploy the core components of the ExtremeXP experiment-driven complex analytics framework. This deliverable reports on the following key functionalities of the framework, providing an update to the description of the previous deliverable of this work package, i.e., D5.2 “Core framework services - Data and knowledge management”:

(i) **Adaptive planning of experiments**, i.e., equipping experiments with adaptive control logic that models which workflows to execute, in which order, how to evaluate such executions, and finally how and when to involve the user in the execution of experiments. This functionality is supported by both the Experiment Modeling and the Experiment Execution subsystems of the ExtremeXP architecture (Figure 1).

(ii) **Selection of the best complex analytics variant for each interaction**, i.e., filtering the number of alternative options to be evaluated in an experiment using historical information and informing the design of new experiments. This is supported by both Experiment Execution and Knowledge Management subsystems of the architecture.

Figure 1: Architecture of ExtremeXP framework (extracted from [AIB+23]).

(iii) **Monitoring of analytics workflows and users.** An ExtremeXP experiment can involve execution of a number of workflows and frequent interactions with users acting as either experiment supervisors, input providers, or result validators. All the data related to such workflows and interactions (workflow execution start & end times, durations, produced logs, metrics and other results, user input and feedback) are monitored and persisted by the

framework, allowing complete traceability and reproducibility of experiments. This is supported by the Experiment Execution, User Interaction, and Knowledge Management subsystems.

(iv) **Scalable scheduling of analytics workflows**, i.e., the execution of workflows in a parallel and sequential manner, with possibility of setting up their execution environment in a flexible and easy way (i.e., via Python virtual environments and containerization). This is supported by the Experiment Execution subsystem.

(v) **Secure management of data and knowledge assets**, such as datasets, user profiles, results, learning outcomes, good practices, etc. that are the inputs and outputs of the workflows executed within an experiment. This is supported by the Knowledge Management subsystem.

1.2 Core components of the ExtremeXP framework

The ExtremeXP experimentation framework is composed of multiple components that interact with each other. Figure 2 provides an overview of such interactions, focusing on the core components developed within WP5 (blue frame).

An experiment in the framework must be either *specified* using the **(1) DSL (Domain-Specific Language) Framework** and, optionally, the **(2) Graphical Editors**, or *generated* using the **(3) Intent-based Editor** (developed within WP4, not described in this document). The DSL framework contains a DSL editor in the form of a Visual Studio Code plugin, for ease of use.

An experiment model is then provided to the **(4) Experimentation Engine**, a Python module, which plays a key role in interpreting the experiment and executing it via requesting the execution of one or more workflows in the **(5) Execution Engine**. The latter is built on top of Proactive Scheduling and Abstraction Layer; however other open-source tools such as Kubeflow could be used instead. The Experimentation Engine receives the results of the execution of the workflows and updates the **(6) Data Abstraction Layer** and the **(7) Decentralized Data Management** with the produced results (metrics and datasets acting as input and outputs to workflows).

Figure 2: Interactions between software tools and components in the ExtremeXP framework. Core components developed with WP5 are marked with blue frame; others with green.

The Data Abstraction Layer (DAL) is a service designed to store, retrieve, and query executed experiments, executed workflows, and handle associated metrics. It uses Elasticsearch¹ as the primary database for storage and querying. On the other hand, the Decentralized Data Management (DDM) provides a holistic solution to manage datasets in ExtremeXP. It contains a Graphical User Interface (GUI) where users can upload and tag datasets to be used as inputs to experiments and is also exposed via an API that is used by the other components to load or save datasets. Internally, it uses Zenoh for decentralized file management.

Results of experiments are visualized via the **(8) Experiment Visualization** component (developed within WP4 and not described in this document) and the **(9) Experiments Cards** component. The latter provides a high-level overview of experiments that have been run so far with the goal to help analysts extract best practices and guide their future experimentations.

Finally, the **(10) Access Control** is a component connected, due to its nature, to all other components and provides a uniform way of performing authentication and authorization in the framework. Internally, it is based on Keycloak, a mature framework.

We emphasize that the architecture of the experimentation framework is highly modular, allowing for the integration with other execution engines, visualization engines, or data backends.

Table 1 summarizes the 8 core components of the ExtremeXP framework and provides a reference to their open-source repositories and corresponding sections in this document.

Table 1: Overview of tools and software components provided by WP5.

Tool/SW Module	Repository	Section
Experimentation Engine	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-experimentation-engine	2
Data Abstraction Layer	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-dal	3
DSL Framework	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-dsl-framework	4
	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-ide	
Graphical Editors	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-portal	4
Execution Engine	https://github.com/ow2-proactive/proactive-python-client	5
Access Control	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-AccessControl	6
Decentralized Data Management	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/DDM	7
Experiment Cards	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremeXP_experimentCards	8

¹ <https://github.com/elastic/elasticsearch>

2 Experimentation Engine

2.1 Main functionalities

The Experimentation Engine (ExpEngine in short) serves as the core component of ExtremeXP's implementing the Continuous Adaptive Experiment Planning functionality. Its primary responsibility is to execute ExtremeXP experiments by orchestrating and evaluating workflows. It takes the form of a Python module published at PyPI².

Figure 3: Class diagram of the Experimentation Engine internal architecture.

Figure 3 presents the class diagram of the module, illustrating its core internal interfaces and their configurable implementations. In particular, the Experimentation Engine provides three interfaces: **DataManager**, **ExecutionWare**, and **DAL** (Data Abstraction Layer).

DataManager handles the retrieval and storage of datasets (files) during experiment execution. Two implementations are currently supported:

- **LocalStorage**: Uses the local file system (of the machine where the experiment is launched) for retrieving and saving datasets. This is useful when using the module as a stand-alone component, i.e., without depending on the Decentralized Data Management (DDM) component of the ExtremeXP framework (Section 7).
- **DDM**: Uses the API endpoints of the DDM component of the ExtremeXP framework (Section 7) for retrieving and saving datasets. Internally, DDM uses the Zenoh framework, making it possible to manage datasets distributed over a cluster of machines. This implementation provides more flexibility for accessing datasets generated via workflows from different components of the framework (e.g., from the Experiment Visualization component).

² <https://pypi.org/project/eexp-engine/>

ExecutionWare handles the scheduling and execution of workflows generated during the execution of an experiment via the Experimentation Engine. Two implementations are currently supported:

- **LocalExec:** Workflows are executed directly on the local machine (where the experiment is launched) as Python processes. This is useful mostly for debugging purposes and offers fewer integration possibilities compared to Proactive.
- **Proactive:** Workflows are transformed into Proactive “jobs” and submitted for execution to Activeeon’s ProActive platform. The Proactive Python client is used for this, which internally connects to ProActive via dedicated endpoints. The Experimentation Engine periodically polls to obtain the status of execution of the submitted workflows.

The **DAL** is an interface for saving and retrieving (i) metadata about experiments and workflows, and (ii) values of produced metrics. It currently has a single implementation that acts as a Python client to the Data Abstraction Layer service of the ExtremeXP framework (Section 3). Once the metadata of an experiment is saved in the Data Abstraction Layer, they can be retrieved by other components of the framework, e.g., the Experiment Visualization and Experiment Cards ones).

Given the above modular and adaptable architecture, the Experimentation Engine performs the following key steps when provided with an experiment definition:

- 1 It parses the experiment definition written in the ExtremeXP Domain-Specific Language (DSL) using textX, a Python tool for working with textual DSLs³.
- 2 It executes the steps of an experiment according to its control logic (in sequence or in parallel). It can do so in a conditional way, i.e., execute steps based on the results of previous ones.
- 3 For each step being executed, it generates the necessary executable workflows, i.e., the workflows consisting of non-abstract, fully parametrized tasks.
- 4 It submits the executable workflows for execution.
- 5 It retrieves the results of each executed workflow (such as metrics values, generated datasets) and saves them alongside the metadata of the experiment and the executed workflows.
- 6 It may submit special types of workflows for execution, which consist of tasks that expect input from users – “user-interaction” tasks. Inputs from users are also saved together with the results of each workflow.

2.2 Instructions for using the Experimentation Engine

This section provides a step-by-step guide for using the ExpEngine for running experiments within the ExtremeXP framework. We used a simple demo experiment to streamline the description of the different steps. This guide provides both

1. a detailed description of the configuration options offered by the ExpEngine to its users (Python programmers);
2. an illustration of an experiment specification using the Domain-Specific Language (DSL) of ExtremeXP; and
3. practical advice on how to run an experiment using the ExtremeXP framework.

Nota bene: The ExpEngine and this guide have been developed and tested on Unix-based systems. Nevertheless, using it in Windows systems should be possible with minimal changes (activating virtual environment in a Windows-specific way, specifying paths with backslashes).

³ <https://textx.github.io/textX/>

Step 0: Preliminaries

Before getting started, make sure that the following are installed in your system:

- Python (version ≥ 3.10)
- Java version 11 or 13, necessary if Proactive is used as executionware (the default option)

Step 1: Set up your development environment

- A. Open a terminal or command prompt and navigate to the directory where you want your project to be created, then create a Python virtual environment via

```
python -m venv <environment_name>
```

Replace `<environment_name>` with your desired name (e.g., “env”).

If you already have a virtual environment created, you can skip this step.

- B. Activate the virtual environment via

```
source <environment_name>/bin/activate
```

- C. Install the `eexp_engine` PyPI package, which corresponds to the latest release of the ExpEngine module, via

```
pip install eexp_engine
```

Note: If you have `eexp_engine` already installed and you want to update it to the latest version, you can do this via

```
pip install eexp_engine --upgrade
```

Step 2: Configure the engine

A number of configuration options have to be set before using the experimentation engine. The best practice is to do so in a file called “`eexp_config.py`” that is imported by the ExpEngine runner script (see Step 3). For convenience, the description of the different options is split in different categories below. The mandatory options are marked with a star (*). An example configuration file is also provided at the end.

A. Main directories

- (*) `EXPERIMENT_LIBRARY_PATH`: The path to the directory that holds the experiment specifications (`.xsp` files). It can be either an absolute path or relative to the runner script.
- (*) `TASK_LIBRARY_PATH`: The path to the directory that holds the tasks referenced by the experiment specifications. It can be either an absolute path or relative to the runner script. Each task is represented by a folder that contains the task specification (`.xsp` file).
- `PYTHON_DEPENDENCIES_RELATIVE_PATH`: The path to the directory that holds any Python sources that act as dependencies to (and therefore are imported by) the Python script of any task. As the name suggests, this path *has to* be specified as relative to the runner script. This is useful for adding Python dependencies to tasks when those dependencies are not available as PyPI packages.
- `DATASET_LIBRARY_RELATIVE_PATH`: The path to the directory that holds files (optionally organized in directories) that act as inputs to tasks, and where files corresponding to outputs of tasks are saved. As the name suggests, this path *has to* be specified as relative to the runner script. This is only used if the `DATASET_MANAGEMENT` is set to `LOCAL`.

B. Helper modules

- `PYTHON_CONDITIONS`: The path to the Python module (file without the “.py” extension) that holds the functions that can be used in the evaluation of conditions in an experiment. This is a dot-separated path that is relative to the runner script. An example of such Python module is available [online](#).
- `PYTHON_CONFIGURATIONS`: The path to the Python module (file without the “.py” extension) that holds any functions used for filtering or generating configurations for spaces. This is a dot-separated path that is relative to the runner script. An example of such module is available [online](#).

C. Execution

- `MAX_WORKFLOWS_IN_PARALLEL_PER_NODE`: An integer that specifies the maximum number of workflows that the engine can run in parallel per node. If omitted, the default value is 1.
- (*) `EXECUTIONWARE`: The name of the module that acts as the execution engine for workflows. Two options are currently available: `PROACTIVE` and `LOCAL`. The first one refers to Activeeon’s Proactive tool, the second to a Python-based implementation of the execution engine which is not full-fledged and has been mostly used so far for testing the functionalities of the engine. We emphasize that, thanks to the flexible and modular design of the engine, other execution engines (based on open-source technologies such as Kubeflow) can be integrated into the engine and used as its `EXECUTIONWARE`.
- `PROACTIVE_URL`, `PROACTIVE_USERNAME`, `PROACTIVE_PASSWORD`: The URL and credentials of the Proactive SDK endpoint. This is only used if the `EXECUTIONWARE` is set to `PROACTIVE`.
- `PROACTIVE_PYTHON_VERSIONS`: A Python dictionary mapping Python version (strings, e.g., “3.8”) to the paths of Python executables on the server that Proactive is installed on (strings, e.g., “/usr/bin/python3.8”). This is only relevant if the `EXECUTIONWARE` is set to `PROACTIVE`.

D. Data management

- (*) `DATA_ABSTRACTION_BASE_URL`: The URL of the service endpoint of the Data Abstraction Layer (Section 3).
- (*) `DATA_ABSTRACTION_ACCESS_TOKEN`: The access token of the service endpoint of the Data Abstraction Layer (Section 3).
- `DATASET_MANAGEMENT`: The name of the module to be used for managing the datasets used in experiments, inputs and (intermediate) outputs. Two options are currently available: `LOCAL` and `DDM`. The first one instructs the engine to manage datasets via its built-in Python implementation. The second one refers to the Decentralized Data Management service (Section 7) based on the Zenoh framework. If omitted, the default value is `LOCAL`.
- `DDM_URL`: The URL of the endpoint of the Decentralized Data Management service (Section 3). This is only relevant if the `DATASET_MANAGEMENT` is set to `DDM`.

E. Logging

- `LOGGING_CONFIG`: A Python dictionary that configures the logging level (`DEBUG`, `INFO`, `WARNING`, `ERROR`, `CRITICAL` or `NOTSET`) for each of the engine modules (parsing, execution, `abstraction_layer`, etc.). ExpEngine uses the default Python logging module for internal logging, this dictionary corresponds to the [dictionary schema of that package](#). If not set, all loggers are configured to have `INFO` level.

Putting everything together, the following is a representative example of a `config.py` specifying all the above options. You can copy this into a file with the same name.

Listing 1: “`config.py`” – main configuration file


```

1. # A. Main directories
2. EXPERIMENT_LIBRARY_PATH = 'library-experiments/tests'
3. TASK_LIBRARY_PATH = 'library-tasks'
4. PYTHON_DEPENDENCIES_RELATIVE_PATH = 'dependencies'
5. DATASET_LIBRARY_RELATIVE_PATH = 'library-datasets'
6.
7. # B. Helper modules
8. PYTHON_CONDITIONS = 'library-tasks.experiment_conditions'
9. PYTHON_CONFIGURATIONS = 'library-tasks.experiment_configurations'
10.
11. # C. Execution
12. MAX_WORKFLOWS_IN_PARALLEL_PER_NODE = 3
13. EXECUTIONWARE = "PROACTIVE"
14. PROACTIVE_URL = "https://proactive.extremexp-icom.intracom-telecom.com"
15. PROACTIVE_USERNAME="admin"
16. PROACTIVE_PASSWORD="Extr3me_XP"
17. PROACTIVE_PYTHON_VERSIONS = {"3.8": "/usr/bin/python3.8"}
18.
19. # D. Data management
20. DATA_ABSTRACTION_BASE_URL = "https://api.dal.extremexp-icom.intracom-telecom.com/api"
21. DATA_ABSTRACTION_ACCESS_TOKEN = 'b7eb45c87af9b4e32f2bdf38f9e605e4b2d20130'
22. DATASET_MANAGEMENT = "LOCAL"
23. DDM_URL = "http://146.124.106.200/api" # not used
24.
25. # E. Logging
26. LOGGING_CONFIG = {
27.     'version': 1,
28.     'loggers': {
29.         'eexp_engine': {
30.             'level': 'DEBUG'
31.         },
32.         'eexp_engine.functions': {
33.             'level': 'DEBUG'
34.         },
35.         'eexp_engine.functions.parsing': {
36.             'level': 'INFO',
37.         },
38.         'eexp_engine.functions.execution': {
39.             'level': 'DEBUG',
40.         },
41.         'eexp_engine.data_abstraction_layer': {
42.             'level': 'DEBUG'
43.         },
44.         'eexp_engine.models': {
45.             'level': 'DEBUG'
46.         },
47.         'eexp_engine.models.experiment': {
48.             'level': 'DEBUG'
49.         },
50.         'eexp_engine.proactive_executionware': {
51.             'level': 'DEBUG'
52.         }
53.     }
54. }

```

Step 3: Create an experiment specification using the ExtremeXP DSL

Create a directory `library-experiments`, another directory `tests` inside it, and a file called `example_exp.xxp` inside `tests`. Copy the DSL code provided below into this file.

Listing 2: “example_exp.xxp” – experiment specification

```

1. workflow DemoWP5Workflow {
2.
3.     START -> Task1 -> Task2 -> END;
4.
5.     task Task1 {
6.         implementation "demo_tasks/DemoWP5Task1";
7.     }
8.
9.     task Task2;
10.
11.    define input data InputFile;
12.    define output data OutputFile;
13.
14.    configure data InputFile {
15.        path "demo_datasets/titanic.json";
16.    }
17.
18.    configure data OutputFile {
19.        path "output/test_local/titanic_once_more.json";
20.    }
21.
22.    InputFile --> Task1.DemoWP5Task1InputFile;
23.    Task1.DemoWP5Task10OutputFile --> Task2.DemoWP5Task2InputFile;
24.    Task2.DemoWP5Task20OutputFile --> OutputFile;
25. }
26.
27. workflow DemoWP5AssembledWorkflow1 from DemoWP5Workflow {
28.     task Task2 {
29.         implementation "demo_tasks/DemoWP5Task1V1";
30.     }
31. }
32.
33. workflow DemoWP5AssembledWorkflow2 from DemoWP5Workflow {
34.     task Task2 {
35.         implementation "demo_tasks/DemoWP5Task1V2";
36.     }
37. }
38.
39. experiment DemoWP5Experiment {
40.
41.     control {
42.         START -> S1 -> S2 -> END;
43.     }

```

```

44.
45.     space S1 of DemoWP5AssembledWorkflow1 {
46.         strategy gridsearch;
47.         param_values demo_param_value = range(4, 6);
48.         task Task1 {
49.             param demo_param = demo_param_values;
50.         }
51.     }
52.
53.     space S2 of DemoWP5AssembledWorkflow2 {
54.         strategy randomsearch;
55.         runs = 1;
56.         param_values demo_param_value = enum(6);
57.         task Task1 {
58.             param demo_param = demo_param_values;
59.         }
60.     }
61. }
62.

```

A description of the above DSL specification follows, together with several general notes about the DSL (in *italics*).

- A. A workflow `DemoWP5Workflow` consisting of two tasks, `Task1` and `Task2`, which are to be executed in a sequence (line 3).

Our DSL also allows the specification of conditional links between tasks via an expression of the form

```
Task1 ?-> "check_task1_result" ? Task2 : Task3 -> Task4;
```

where `check_task1_result` is a condition specified as Python function in the module linked by the `PYTHON_CONDITIONS` option in `config.py`, `Task2` is the task to be executed if the condition returns true, `Task3` if it returns false, and `Task4` is to be executed after either `Task2` or `Task3`.

- B. `Task1`'s implementation is provided alongside its definition (lines 5-7), whereas `Task2` on the contrary is only defined, without any implementation (line 9).

A task can be defined with or without an implementation. An implementation is a path, relative to the one defined in the `TASK_LIBRARY_PATH` in the `config.py`, to the folder that contains the specification of the task (`.xsp` file).

- C. One input and one output, `InputFile` and `OutputFile`, are first defined (lines 11-12) and then configured (lines 14-20) for this workflow. This input and output are associated with the corresponding tasks of the workflow, alongside the rest of the data that flows between the two tasks (lines 22-24).

A workflow can have several inputs and outputs. An input is read by one task, and an output is generated by one task. Tasks can also pass datasets between each other as specified in the data flow of the workflow. When setting the `DATASET_MANAGEMENT` to `LOCAL`, inputs and outputs are configured via their `path` attribute (as in the example). If `DDM` is used, they must be configured via their `zenoh_name` and `zenoh_project` attributes ([online example](#)).

- D. Two more workflows are also defined: DemoWP5AssembledWorkflow1 and DemoWP5AssembledWorkflow1 (lines 26-36). They both inherit from DemoWP5Workflow and set the implementation of Task2. Since the implementation of all their tasks is provided, both of those workflows are “assembled” workflows.
- E. An experiment DemoWP5Experiment is also defined (lines 39-61). Its control logic is first defined as a sequence of two nodes, S1 and S2 (lines 41-43).

The control logic of an experiment specifies tasks executed both in sequence and in parallel (online example). An example of the latter is

```
START -> (S1 || S2) -> END;
```

For a complete specification of an experiment with parallel nodes, see [this online example](#).

Moreover, the control logic can also include simple conditional links of the form

```
S1 ?-> S2 { condition "check_results_less_than 100" };
```

Here, node S1 is followed by node S2 only if the result of the condition is true. Similar to the specification of conditions in the control flow of a workflow, check_results_less_than must be specified as Python function (with one argument) in the module linked by the PYTHON_CONDITIONS option in config.py.

Finally, a node can be either a space (as in our example) or an experiment-level task. While the former generates in principle several jobs to be executed (where a job is an executed workflow with potentially several tasks), the latter is translated by the engine into a single job with a single task. See [this online example](#) for an experiment that involves experiment-level tasks.

- F. Within this experiment, two spaces are defined, S1 and S2. The first one is associated with the assembled workflow DemoWP5AssembledWorkflow1, while the second one is associated with the assembled workflow DemoWP5AssembledWorkflow2. S1 is specified to perform **grid search** over the values of parameter demo_param of Task1, which are defined by the range construct to be 4 and 5 (6 is excluded). On the other side, S2 is specified to perform 1 run of **random search** over the values of the same parameter of the same task, which are now defined by the enum construct to be only 6 (just for showcasing).

A space generates one or more jobs (or “executed workflows”) by parametrizing the tasks of the assembled workflow it is associated with. A space is specified via its strategy (gridsearch and randomsearch are supported for now) and by one or more param_values. Grid search systematically explores all combinations of parameter values, whereas random search selects combinations of parameter values at random in every iteration. Grid search should be chosen when full coverage of a search space is important; random search is useful when the search space is too large to be systematically explored or when there is limited knowledge about which values are most promising.

Parameter values are specified either with the range or the enum construct. Range is equivalent to the Python range function and accepts three numeric parameters: a start, an end, and a step (optional; default is 1, as in our example). It generates a sequence of numbers by starting from the start and incrementing according to the step until reaching the end (excluding the end). Enum, on the other hand, expects a list of values, which can be numbers or strings.

The generation of the search space via the param_values can be constraining: in some ExtremeXP use cases, there was the need to programmatically exclude certain configurations from a search space or add certain configurations to a search space. For this, we provide two more constructs that can be used within a space definition: filter

and generator. They are both followed by a string that corresponds to the name of the function to be used for filtering or generation, respectively. These functions are defined in the module linked by the `PYTHON_CONFIGURATIONS` option in `config.py`.

Step 4: Create the task specifications

Next, create another directory `library-tasks`, and another one `demo_tasks` inside it. In `demo_tasks`, create three more directories: `DemoWP5Task1` and `DemoWP5Task2V1` and `DemoWP5Task2V2`. Within `DemoWP5Task1`, add the following file.

Listing 3: “task.xxp” – task specification

```

1. task DemoWP5Task1 {
2.     define input data DemoWP5Task1InputFile;
3.     define output data DemoWP5Task1OutputFile;
4.
5.     define param demo_param {
6.         type Integer;
7.         default 10;
8.         range (4, 20, 2);
9.     }
10.
11.    define metric ParamIncreasedBy5 {
12.        kind single-value;
13.        type Integer;
14.    }
15.
16.    implementation "demo_tasks/DemoWP5Task1/task.py";
17.    python_version "3.8";
18. }
19.

```

This task specification consists of the following:

- A. The task’s name (`DemoWP5Task1`), a single input (`DemoWP5Task1InputFile`), a single output (`DemoWP5Task1OutputFile`), a single parameter (`demo_param`), and a single metric (`ParamIncreasedBy5`) – lines 1-14.

A task always has a single name but can have several inputs, outputs, parameters, and metrics. Input and outputs are specified only by their name. Parameters need a name, a type (Integer, String, or Float), a default value, and domain.

A parameter domain is specified either using the keyword `range` (line 8) or `enum`, like the specification of `param_values` (Step 3). `Range` can only be used for parameters of type `Integer` or `Float`, whereas `enum` can be used with any type of parameters.

A metric is specified by its name, kind (`single-value` or `series`), type (`Integer`, `String`, or `Float`), and, optionally, its `semanticType` (not shown in the example). The last is meant for providing common metrics for comparability across experiments. So far, the engine supports the following semantic types (but the list is extensible): `ML_Accuracy`, `ML_Recall`, `ML_Precision`, `ML_F1Score`, and `Model_TrainingTime`.

- B. The task’s implementation path and python version – lines 16-17. The path here points to `task.py` which is in the same folder as `task.xxp`, but this is just a convention: it could point to any path, relative to the one defined in the `TASK_LIBRARY_PATH` in the `config.py`. Also,

since python version 3.8 is specified, this must be present in the PROACTIVE_PYTHON_VERSIONS dictionary in the config.py.

Together with the path and the python version, a task's specification can also contain information to configure a Python virtual environment and to load additional Python dependencies (used in the main implementation script). Examples:

```
venv "demo_tasks/DemoWP5Task1/requirements.txt";
```

Here, we assume that a requirements.txt is present in the same folder as task.xxp (the provided path is relative to the one defined in the TASK_LIBRARY_PATH in config.py). This holds the Python requirements that can be installed via pip, a well-known mechanism for installing external dependencies in Python. The file format of such file is described [online](#).

```
dependency "DemoWP5Task1/deps/**";
```

Here, the provided path is relative to the one defined in the PYTHON_DEPENDENCIES_RELATIVE_PATH in the config.py. It must also end in "" – this is a requirement from Proactive and may change in the future releases of the engine. By adding the above line, any directory and Python file inside the deps folder (recursively) can be imported via the implementation of the task.*

Retrieve the task specifications for the other two tasks from GitHub ([DemoWP5Task2V1](#) and [DemoWP5Task2V2](#)) and add them to the respective folders.

Step 5: Provide the task implementations

The next step is to add the task implementation. Add the following file in the folder of DemoWP5Task1, next to task.xxp. Also, retrieve the implementations of the other two files (DemoWP5Task2V1 and DemoWP5Task2V2) and add them to the respective folders.

Listing 4: "task.py" – corresponding task implementation

```
1. [sys.path.append(os.path.join(os.getcwd(), folder)) for folder in
   variables.get("dependent_modules_folders").split(",")]
2. import proactive_helper as ph
3.
4. print("Running DemoWP5Task1")
5.
6. dataset = ph.load_dataset(variables, resultMap, "DemoWP5Task1InputFile")
7.
8. demo_param_value = variables.get("demo_param_value")
9. print(f"with value of demo_param: {demo_param_value}")
10.
11. increment = 5
12. metric_name = "ParamIncreasedBy5"
13.
14. print (f"Increasing this parameter by {increment} and adding the result to
   the metric {metric_name}")
15. resultMap.put(metric_name, int(demo_param) + increment)
16.
17. ph.save_dataset(variables, resultMap, "DemoWP5Task10utputFile", dataset)
18.
```

Note the following regarding this task implementation.

- A. The first two lines are needed for importing `proactive_helper`, a Python module of the ExpEngine that allows for working programmatically with inputs and outputs, i.e., to load and save datasets.
- B. Line 6 loads the dataset `DemoWP5Task1InputFile`, assuming that it is specified as input in the task's specification, while line 17 saves the dataset `DemoWP5Task1InputFile`, assuming that it is specified as output. The paths for loading and saving these files are specified in the experiment specification.

The `proactive_helper` also supports reading and writing several datasets at once via the `load_datasets` and `save_datasets` functions, which are however only supported when using DDM as `DATASET_MANAGEMENT`. Check these online examples for more information: [load_datasets](#), [save_datasets](#).

- C. Line 8 reads the value of the parameter `demo_param`, assuming that a parameter with the same name is defined in the task's specification and its value is populated via a space in the experiment specification.
- D. Line 15 writes the value of the metric `ParamIncreasedBy5`, assuming that a metric with the same name is defined in the task's specification.

Step 6: Create a runner file and run the experiment

Create a file `run_experiment.py` in the root folder of your project. Copy the code provided below into this file.

Listing 5: "run_experiment.py"

```
1. from eexp_engine import client
2. import eexp_config
3.
4. exp_name = 'example_exp'
5. client.run(__file__, exp_name, eexp_config)
```

Execute the above in the terminal via `python run_experiment.py`, after ensuring that you have activated the virtual environment that you created in step 1.

Step 7: Verify output of experiment

The output that you see in the console depends on the logging configuration (step 2). However, in any case, you should see the following result printed at the end.

Listing 6: Result of a single run of the ExpEngine.

```
{
  'S1': {
    1: {
      'configuration': {
        'demo_param_values': 4
      },
      'result': {
        'DemoWP5Task1OutputFile': '../DemoWP5Task1OutputFile',
        'DemoWP5Task2OutputFile': '../titanic_once_more.json',
        'ParamIncreasedBy5': 9
      }
    }
  }
}
```

```

    },
    2: {
      'configuration': {
        'demo_param_values': 5
      },
      'result': {
        'DemoWP5Task1OutputFile': '../DemoWP5Task1OutputFile',
        'DemoWP5Task2OutputFile': '../titanic_once_more.json',
        'ParamIncreasedBy5': 10
      }
    }
  },
  'S2': {
    1: {
      'configuration': {
        'demo_param_values': 6
      },
      'result': {
        'DemoWP5Task1OutputFile': '../DemoWP5Task1OutputFile',
        'DemoWP5Task2OutputFile': '../titanic_once_more.json',
        'ParamIncreasedBy5': 11
      }
    }
  }
}

```

Here, you can verify that S1 generated 2 jobs where the `demo_param_value` was set to 4 and 5 and the value of metric `ParamIncreasedBy5` was set, after execution, to 9 and 10, respectively. Then, S2 generated 1 job where the `demo_param_value` was set to 6 and the value of metric `ParamIncreasedBy5` was set, after execution, to 11.

2.3 Experimentation Engine as a service

As already mentioned in Section 2.1, the Experimentation Engine is a Python module published at PyPI. By importing its client and its configuration file, any Python programmer can make use of it and launch ExtremeXP experiments from a Python script (Listing 5).

However, the ExpEngine can also be used as a service, so that experiments can be launched via the graphical interfaces offered by the ExtremeXP portal, i.e., the web application that acts as a single entry point of the different interfaces offered by the different components of the ExtremeXP framework. From the portal, which will be described in detail in the next deliverable of WP6, a user can launch experiments by using the ExpEngine as a service.

When taking the form of a service, the ExpEngine exposes an API with the five endpoints shown in Figure and described below.

GET	/exp/run/{experiment_name}	Run an experiment	▼
GET	/exp/experiment/kill/{experiment_id}	Kill an experiment	▼
GET	/exp/experiment/pause/{experiment_id}	Pause an experiment	▼
GET	/exp/experiment/resume/{experiment_id}	Resume an experiment	▼
GET	/exp/workflow/kill/{workflow_id}	Kill a workflow	▼
GET	/exp/workflow/pause/{workflow_id}	Pause a workflow	▼
GET	/exp/workflow/resume/{workflow_id}	Resume a workflow	▼

Figure 4: OpenAPI (Swagger) API for the ExpEngine service.

- **/exp/run/{experiment_name}**: Start a new experiment based on the experiment specification (i.e., DSL file) of the given name. This returns an experiment id corresponding to the ID of the instantiated, running experiment (not of its specification) as found in the DAL. This ID can be used in the next three endpoints.
- **/exp/experiment/kill/{experiment_id}**: Stop and cancel the execution of a running experiment with the provided id. This can be used, e.g., when an experiment contains a bug or memory leak.
- **/exp/experiment/pause/{experiment_id}**: Stop the execution of a running experiment with the provided id, but do not cancel the experiment. This can be used, e.g., if the execution of another experiment needs to be prioritized.
- **/exp/experiment/resume/{experiment_id}**: Continue the execution of a paused experiment with the provided id.
- **/exp/workflow/kill/{workflow_id}**: Cancel the execution of the workflow with the provided id within an experiment. If the workflow has already been run, this has no effect; if the workflow is currently running, then its execution is interrupted and cancelled; if the workflow is scheduled to be run in the future, it is cancelled. Useful in case a workflow run is no longer needed, or in case of a workflow encountering a bug or memory leak.
- **/exp/workflow/pause/{workflow_id}**: Step the execution of the workflow with the provided id, but do not cancel it. Like pausing experiments, this can be used e.g., to prioritize other workshops.
- **/exp/workflow/resume/{workflow_id}**: Continue the execution of a paused workflow with the provided id.

A link to the complete ExpEngine API documentation is provided in the Appendix (Section 11).

3 Data Abstraction Layer

The Data Abstraction Layer (DAL) is a service designed to store, retrieve, and query executed experiments, executed workflows, and handle associated metrics. It provides structured, authenticated endpoints for storing, updating, and retrieving experimental data, workflows, and metrics. DAL represents a foundational interface between experimentation engines, execution platforms, and visualization modules, enabling traceability, repeatability, and systematic aggregation of experiment results. DAL is accessible via a REST API.

The base API server is:

<http://extremexp-icom.intracom-telecom.com:8445/api/>

Authentication is required via access tokens, retrievable from:

<http://extremexp-icom.intracom-telecom.com:8443/login>

3.1 DAL structure

To allow for flexibility in design and prototyping, we allow early versions of experiments to be run without the results being stored in DAL. However, it is strongly recommended that once the experiments are run to provide any data, the usage of DAL should be switched on.

The DAL supports traceability and repeatability through a well-defined API structure that aligns with experiment execution flows.

Below, the API Interaction Process is presented (and visualized in Figure 5):

1. Start a New Experiment

The engine issues a PUT request to the /experiments endpoint. It contains the DSL specification of the experiment and returns an (auto-generated) experiment id.

2. Create and Register Workflows

For each workflow, a PUT request is made to the /workflow endpoint. The request contains the ID of the experiment the workflow belongs to and returns an (auto-generated) workflow id.

3. Manage Workflows and Parameters

Workflows include various parameters and configurations. The engine updates or queries these workflows using appropriate endpoints, ensuring they are properly associated and managed throughout their lifecycle.

4. Metrics Collection and Aggregation

Metrics associated with the workflows are collected and stored for analysis. The engine may use additional endpoints to manage, update, or retrieve aggregated metrics as needed.

HTTP Method Summary:

- PUT: Create or update elements (201 Created)
- GET: Retrieve elements (200 OK)
- POST: Update elements or execute queries

Figure 5 Interacting with DAL

A link to the complete DAL API documentation is provided in the Appendix (Section 11).

3.2 Data model used by the Data Abstraction Layer

DAL stores the executed experiments as “snapshots,” together with a whole environment (inputs and outputs). This section presents a data model (defined via a meta-model) used in DAL. The implementation of DAL is discussed in Section 3.3.

Figure 6 shows the meta-model of the data model used in DAL. Importantly, the experiments are stored in DAL unstructured, i.e., as BLOBs, but the actual structure of the experiment (and its workflows) can be obtained via DMS (see Section 3.4).

To allow for searching the executed experiments by their various characteristics (e.g., datasets used, algorithms used, types of experiment, user involved, etc.), the executed experiment blob is annotated by key-value pairs, each of which represents one of these characteristics. This is unstructured but allows for indexing in no-SQL databases. These characteristics are derived from the experiment workflow (which is stored as the BLOB).

In detail, the structure of DAL is as follows (in the meta-model description, for better readability of the text, we omit the “meta” prefix when describing the meta-model elements, i.e., meta-class is referred to as a class, meta-attribute as an attribute, etc.) To further enhance the readability, white classes in Figure 6 are abstract, while colored ones are non-abstract.

Figure 6 DAL's data layer meta-model.

The **ExecutedEntity** is an abstract class that represents an executed experiment (either the whole one or its part). Its attributes are as follows:

- **name** – refers to the name of the executed entity. Via the **name**, the entity may be searched in the Design Model Storage.
- **start, end** – refer to the timestamps of the start of the execution of the entity and the end of its execution. The two are necessary as it is expected that the same workflow might be executed many times.
- **comment** – contains any textual comments a user wants to add.

Concrete subclasses of **ExecutedEntity** are the **ExecutedWorkflow** and **ExecutedTask**. The **ExecutedWorkflow** represents a whole executed workflow. It adds the **deployedWorkflow** attribute, which contains a serialized workflow definition. Also, it may refer to several **ExecutedTasks**. The **ExecutedTask** represents a single executed *primitive* task (primitive in this context means a task that is not composed of any subtask and is directly implemented, e.g., as an executable file or a service) that is executed as a part of a workflow. Within the **ExecutedWorkflow**, the **ExecutedTasks** are not held in any order; their ordering can be achieved via the **start** and **end** timestamps.

The **ExecutedEntity** (workflow or task) is associated with inputs and outputs. The **Input** and **Output** classes are abstract and serve as a common input/output representation. The particular kinds are **Parameter** and **InputDataset** for inputs and **Metric** and **OutputDataset** for outputs. As the names suggest, the **InputDataset** and **OutputDataset** represent datasets. Datasets are not stored directly in DAL but only referenced to the Dataset Storage (see the framework architecture in Deliverable D2.1) via the **data** attribute of the **InputDataset/OutputDataset**. The **Parameter** is used for values that are passed to the parameters of workflows/tasks (see the Workflows meta-model in Deliverable D2.1). The **Metric** is a value generated from a workflow/task as a Metric (see the Workflows meta-model in Deliverable D2.1). Finally, the **IndexedData** are values that are “drawn out” from a workflow/task to be indexed and further used by tools (e.g., visualizer). The characteristics used for indexing the workflow are kept in the **IndexedData** class which is attached with 1-to-many cardinality to the **ExecutedEntity**.

Figure 7 shows part of the DAL meta-model used to represent types of values in the **Metric**. The meaning of the individual classes is obvious from their names.

Figure 7 Meta-model of data types used in DAL.

3.3 DAL Implementation

DAL is implemented with the help of the IVIS platform⁴ [BBH+20]. The high-level view of the IVIS architecture is shown in Figure 8 and shows that IVIS is a client-server application with the client frontend running in the web-browser and the server backend running in a cloud.

Figure 8 IVIS architecture.

The backend is responsible for data management and offers an API to the frontend. It serves as the executor and coordinator for plugins that carry out data processing and analysis tasks. It collects data from different sources, such as sensors, either by actively retrieving them from these sensors and their gateways or by passively receiving it through an API that allows these devices to push data to it. Once the data is collected, it is organized within Elasticsearch, a distributed search engine that manages data searches and real-time data aggregations needed by the frontend.

The web-based front-end features both an administrative platform and data visualizations through user dashboards, referred to as panels. This administrative section offers management options for settings like tenants, users, and permissions. Furthermore, it includes a streamlined development environment for creating and developing new visualizations and data processing activities. Access to these visualizations is available directly through the integrated web portal or

⁴ <https://github.com/smartarch/ivis-core>

indirectly via a third-party interface that incorporates the visualizations from the system as an HTML iFrame.

The figure also shows the data server, which stores data from the data model described in the previous section. As mentioned, data is accessible via API.

Technically, DAL is implemented as a plugin to IVIS. It exploits the IVIS extension mechanism, which allows plugins to hook into internal events. It is hooked to the API layer, which extends with the API calls listed in Table 2. These API calls are connected to the data store layer of IVIS, which takes care of indexing data (in this case experiment descriptors and metrics) in the Elasticsearch storage. To this end, IVIS is extended to support the storage of the serialized ExecutedWorkflow (as a blob) and for indexing features extracted from the executed workflow, as in Figure 6 (represented as IndexData instances).

The architecture supports modular interactions between experiment definitions, execution traces, and result evaluations.

Table 2 DAL API endpoints.

Resource	Path Variable	PUT	POST	GET
experiments	–	Create	–	List All
experiments/{id}	experimentId	–	Update	Read
workflows	–	Create	–	List All
workflows/{id}	workflowId	–	Update	Read
metrics	–	Create	–	List All
metrics/{id}	metricId	–	Update	Read
metrics-data/{id}	metricId	Add Records	–	–

3.4 Design Model Storage

The Design Model Storage (DMS) is part of the DAL. The DMS allows for converting information about executed experiments and workflows into various formats. The internal implementation of DMS is extensible, and new formats can thus be easily added.

The primary supported format is DSL (see Section 4).

The other supported format is JSON (which is used by other tools created in the project). When a user retrieves a stored experiment, the DMS performs the conversion on the fly, returning the corresponding JSON. This approach enables users to modify the DSL and always receive updated conversions.

DMS also supports the conversion of workflows into images (SVGs in particular), providing visual representations of experimental workflows. Internally, this conversion is based on the DSL framework (described in Section 4).

From the usage point of view, DMS is not intended to be used directly. It is an internal component of DAL, which is called within several API calls. Namely, when an experiment's information is required and the experiment description is not available in the JSON format (which can occur in a situation the description was provided via DSL only when the experiment was initially stored), DMS is asked to generate the JSON format.

On the code level, DMS can be seen as an associative array, where the keys are the names of the stored elements (experiments, workflows) and values are their representations (as already mentioned, each element can have multiple representations).

4 DSL Framework and Graphical Editors

In this section, we describe the DSL framework together with the DSL editor, and the Graphical Editors, as all of them serve for specifying workflows and experiments.

4.1 DSL Framework

The DSL framework is composed of multiple components, which together allow for the preparation and modification of workflow and experiment descriptions using the ExtremeXP DSL. This DSL is the workflow/experiments description language designed within the project, and it is described in detail in Deliverable D2.1 [AIB+23].

Figure 9 overviews the components of the DSL framework.

Figure 9 DSL Framework and DSL Editor (IDE).

The most visible component is the IDE (Integrated Development Environment) for preparing workflows/experiments. It is the VSCode IDE, to which we developed an extension that provides support for syntax highlighting, syntax and semantics checking, context help, etc., for workflows and experiments. Figure 10 shows a screenshot of the IDE with multiple workflows in an experiment. Figure 11 shows another screenshot, which illustrates the semantics' checks performed as the user edits the workflow/experiment.


```

1 workflow ComplexControlM {
2
3   task Task1 {
4     implementation "Testcase_task1";
5   }
6
7   task Task2;
8
9   START -> Task1 -> Task2 -> END;
10
11 }
12
13 workflow ComplexControlAM1 from ComplexControlM {
14   task Task2 {
15     implementation "Testcase_task2_v1";
16   }
17 }
18
19 workflow ComplexControlAM2 from ComplexControlM {
20   task Task2 {
21     implementation "Testcase_task2_v2";
22   }
23 }
24
25 experiment ComplexControlExp1 {
26   intent testComplexControl;
27
28   control {
29     START -> (S1 || S2);
30   }
31
32   space S1 of ComplexControlAM1 {
33     strategy gridsearch;
34     param param1_vp = enum(2, 5, 1);
35     task Task1 {
36       param param1 = param1_vp;
37     }
38   }
39
40   space S2 of ComplexControlAM2 {
41     strategy gridsearch;
42     param param1_vp = range(3, 6);
43     task Task1 {
44       param param1 = param1_vp;
45     }
46   }
47
48 }
    
```

Figure 10: DSL Editor (IDE).


```

3 workflow CS_surrogate_model_DEMO {
4
5   task TrainModelAPI;
6
7   task ReadMetrics {
8     implementation "UC1.surrogate_model.ReadMetricsAPI";
9   }
10
11 // DATA
12 define input data ExternalDataFile;
13
14 // DATA CONNECTIONS
15 ExternalDataFile --> TrainModelAPI.FileToRead;
16 TrainModelAPI.jobID --> ReadMetrics.jobID;
17 TrainModelAPI.DataVolumeRatio --> ReadMetrics.DataVolumeRatio;
18 }
19
20 workflow DemoAPI {
21   implementation "UC1.surrogate_model.TrainModelAPI";
22 }
23
24 experiment EXP {
25   intent FindBestClassifier;
26
27   control {
28     START -> S1 -> S2 -> END;
29   }
30
31   space S1 of TrainDemoAPI {
32     strategy gridsearch;
    
```

Figure 11: The language server detects DSL mistakes made by users and marks them in red. In this case, the user is referring to a non-existent task.

Technically, the support for syntax and semantics checks is implemented via a language server⁵. The IDE communicates with language server via the language server protocol (LSP), which is today's de facto standard on how to add support for new languages to IDEs and editors, and most of the contemporary IDEs contain LSP clients. The created language server can thus be used with any other IDE supporting LSP.

Our language server is developed using the meta-model (designed using EMF⁶) of the workflows/experiments (the meta-model is described in Deliverable D2.1 [AIB+23]). Internally, the server uses the Xtext framework⁷, which is an open-source framework for developing programming languages and domain-specific languages (DSLs). Developed as part of EMF, Xtext enables software engineers to define the grammar of a language, generate parsers, editors, and other tooling, and seamlessly integrate these languages into the Eclipse IDE but also use them separately. Its core strength lies in making language engineering more efficient by automating much of the infrastructure traditionally required for custom languages and by providing a rich development environment almost “for free.”

At its core, Xtext lets users define a language using a simple, EBNF-inspired grammar. From this definition, Xtext automatically generates a parser and an abstract syntax tree (AST) model based on EMF. It also produces a fully functional, customizable editor for Eclipse, complete with syntax highlighting, code completion, validation, navigation, etc., but it can also produce the language server (as it is used in our case). Additionally, Xtext supports integration with other tooling such as code generators, static analyzers, etc.

Below, a small part of the Xtext grammar for our DSL is shown (the complete version is available in the GitHub repository⁸).

Listing 7: Xtext grammar example

```
Workflow:
    CompositeWorkflow | TaskSpecification | AssembledWorkflow
;

CompositeWorkflow:
    'workflow' name=ID '{'
    (
        // shared members (i.e., super members)
        inputs += InputData |
        outputs += OutputData |

        // dedicated members
        tasks += Task |
        dataConfigurations += DataConfiguration |
        links += Link |
        dataLinks += DataLink |
        nodes += Node
    )*
    '}'
;

AssembledWorkflow:
    'workflow' name=ID 'from' parent=[Workflow] '{'
    (
        // shared members (i.e., super members)
```

⁵ <https://microsoft.github.io/language-server-protocol/>

⁶ <https://eclipse.dev/emf/>

⁷ <https://eclipse.dev/Xtext/>

⁸ <https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-dsl-framework/blob/main/eu.extremexp.dsl.parent/eu.extremexp.dsl/src/eu/extremexp/dsl/XDSL.xtext>

```

        inputs += InputData           |
        outputs += OutputData        |

        // dedicated members
        taskConfigurations += TaskConfiguration

    }
}
;

```

The IDE is deployed in servers provided by ICOM and is accessible via this endpoint: <https://ide.extremexp-icom.intracom-telecom.com>

4.2 Graphical Editors

In ExtremeXP, workflows and experiments are primarily specified using the **textual** editor that comes with the DSL framework (Section 4.1). As an alternative to this, ExtremeXP also provides graphical tools for specifying workflows and experiments which target less tech-savvy end users. They provide an intuitive interface that can be used without knowing or learning the ExtremeXP DSL. These tools are the Workflow Graphical Editor and the Experiment Designer.

4.2.1 Workflow Graphical Editor

This is a web application based on React Flow⁹ that allows for specifying workflows graphically. This tool was developed during the first half of the project and is thoroughly described in Section 2.5 of D5.2 [KGR+24]. We provide here only an overview of its main functionalities.

The Workflow Graphical Editor allows for dragging and dropping tasks, operators, and datasets to a canvas and connecting them to each other to form workflows (Figure 12). It supports creating both simple and composite tasks, i.e., tasks composed of workflows. The latter can be opened in their own tabs.

Figure 12: Workflow Graphical Editor (extracted from [KGR+24]).

⁹ <https://reactflow.dev/>

By double-clicking on a task, the editor allows for (i) specifying alternative implementations for this task, (ii) specifying tunable parameters for each for each alternative implementation, defined via their name, data type, and domain of permissible values.

The workflow specifications built with the Workflow Graphical Editor are automatically translated into DSL files that can be viewed and, if needed, altered via the DSL framework. This way the Workflow Graphical Editor can act as starting point for intuitive specification and overview of complex workflows. Such workflows are used in experiments specified directly using the DSL framework or via Experiment Designer, described next.

4.2.2 Experiment Designer

This is a React¹⁰ web application that supports the specification of experiments in ExtremeXP. An experiment consists of a number of actions (called spaces¹¹) executed in parallel or in a sequence forming the control flow of the experiment. Each space corresponds to the execution of a number of concrete workflows, derived via (i) selecting a workflow specification, (i) choosing an implementation for each of the workflow's tasks (in case a task has more than one alternative implementations), (ii) choosing a value for each parameter of each chosen task implementation. The latter happens with the help of a search algorithm such as random search, grid search, or Bayesian optimization.

Given the above, the Experiment Designer must first allow users to create spaces executed in parallel and in sequence. This is achieved via relying on the concept of a **step**, which is a container of spaces running in parallel. In particular, the user can specify (by clicking on the “Add step” button) one or more steps in an experiment. These steps are always executed in sequence (Figure 13). Then, within each step, the user can specify one or more spaces (via the “+” button on the top right of the step). Spaces specified in the same step are always executed in parallel when that step is active. This design offers the possibility of creating spaces that run completely in sequence (via creating several steps with only a single space in each of them), completely in parallel (via creating a single step and adding all spaces in it), and both in sequence and in parallel – which was the requirement of the tool.

¹⁰ <https://react.dev/>

¹¹ Short for “exploration space”, see D2.1 [AIB+23]

Figure 13: Experiment specification with two steps and five spaces contained in them.

For each space, the user needs to first import the workflow specification that will be associated with the space. The user chooses from a list of workflow specifications (Figure 14), created either via the Workflow Graphical Editor or the DSL Framework; the tasks of the chosen specification are shown in a sequence, from top to bottom (Figure 15).

Figure 14: Selecting from list of three existing workflows when configuring a space.

The user then selects the implementation of each task by clicking on the corresponding radio button (Figure 15). When a task has a single implementation, this is preselected, and the user can omit this step.

Figure 15: Selecting between two alternative implementations of the TrainModel task.

Finally, the user provides values for each parameter of the chosen task implementations (Figure 16). After the workflow is configured, the user needs to also select the search strategy for the space, choosing from a dropdown list of strategies that include grid search (default option), random search, and others (Figure 17).

Figure 16: Specifying values for each parameter of the chosen implementation.

Figure 17: Specifying the search strategy to be used in a space.

Similar to workflows specified via the Workflow Graphical Editor, experiments specified via the Experiments Designer are automatically translated into DSL files that can be viewed and, if needed, altered using the DSL framework and its textual editor. This provides full flexibility to users who may prefer either starting from the graphical editors and then using the DSL framework, or using only the graphical editors, or finally using only the DSL framework.

5 Runtime for Scheduling Complex Workflows

As already mentioned in previous sections, an ExtremeXP experiment essentially consists of several potentially complex analytics workflows that need to be run and compared to each other. The runtime component for scheduling complex workflows is part of the Experiment Execution block of the ExtremeXP architecture shown in Figure 1 and implements the scheduling, execution, and monitoring of workflows that can be run on various types of computing resources, ranging from local machines to large-scale cloud infrastructures. The component is based on ProActive Workflows & Scheduling (PWS), a tool designed for orchestrating and automating tasks across distributed computing environments. PWS is particularly well-suited for applications in big data analysis, scientific research, and machine learning, where tasks can be computationally intensive and may need to be executed in a specific order or in parallel to optimize performance and resource utilization. It offers a comprehensive suite of features, including a powerful Python SDK with a declarative syntax, designed to improve operational efficiency, reduce costs, and increase agility for businesses.

5.1 Overall Architecture of the PWS

PWS is composed of a central server (the Scheduler) that manages the task queues and orchestrates the execution across available resources, which are managed by the Resource Manager. The user interacts with the system through a client interface, which could be a web portal, a command-line interface, or an API, to submit workflows and monitor their execution. This architecture (Figure 4) ensures that ProActive can efficiently manage and execute a large number of tasks across diverse computing environments, making it a powerful tool for automating complex workflows in various domains.

Figure 4 Architecture of ProActive Workflows & Scheduling System

The key components of the PWS architecture are:

Workflow Studio: This visual interface allows users to design and configure workflows by defining tasks, dependencies, and execution logic. It supports various programming languages and includes drag-and-drop functionality for ease of use.

Resource Manager: It provides centralized control over all resources, including physical machines, virtual machines, containers, and cloud resources. It allows for the dynamic allocation and deallocation of resources based on the needs of the executing workflows, ensuring efficient use of available computing power.

Scheduling Engine: It is responsible for managing the execution of tasks defined in workflows. It ensures that tasks are executed in the correct order, respecting their dependencies, and optimally utilizing available computing resources. The scheduler can handle dynamic resource availability changes and can adapt the execution strategy in real time to optimize performance.

Execution Environment (Agent): It is where tasks are run. ProActive supports a diverse set of execution environments, allowing tasks to be executed on anything from a single laptop to a distributed cloud infrastructure. The system abstracts the complexities of the computing environment, providing a consistent interface for task execution.

Monitoring and Control: Offers comprehensive monitoring and control capabilities, allowing users to track the progress of workflows, inspect the output of tasks, and intervene manually if necessary. This is crucial for long running or complex workflows where issues may need to be addressed in real time.

Security: Protects sensitive data and computing resources. The system supports authentication, authorization, and secure communication, ensuring that only authorized users can access and execute workflows.

Extensibility and Integration: Designed to be extensible and can be integrated with other systems and software. This allows users to incorporate custom tasks, use ProActive in conjunction with existing tools, and extend the system's capabilities to meet specific requirements.

5.2 ProActive AI Orchestration

ProActive AI Orchestration (PAIO) is a platform designed to facilitate the orchestration and automation of AI workflows across distributed computing environments. It is part of the broader PWS ecosystem, which specializes in managing complex job executions, resource management, and task scheduling on various infrastructures, including clouds, clusters, and hybrid environments.

Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) automation within the PWS framework enhances the management of complex, data-driven processes. This integration leverages AI's capabilities to analyze data, make predictions, and recognize patterns, thereby enriching the ecosystem with intelligent decision-making. The orchestration capability of ProActive ensures the efficient coordination of diverse tasks and processes across multiple systems and environments. It orchestrates workflows to ensure tasks are executed in an optimal sequence, considering dependencies and the availability of resources. This seamless orchestration and AI-driven automation streamlines the execution of workflows, making complex task management more efficient and responsive to dynamic conditions.

Figure 5 Designing Predictive Models with ProActive's Machine Learning Studio

PAIO is highly adaptable, making it suitable for a wide range of industries and applications, from IT operations and DevOps to data analytics and beyond. Its scalable nature allows it to handle workflows of varying complexities, from simple task automation to orchestrating large-scale, data-intensive processes. PAIO supports the following use cases:

Automated Machine Learning (AutoML): Automating the process of applying machine learning to real-world problems, including automatic model selection, hyperparameter tuning, and model validation.

Data Pipeline Automation: Orchestrating complex data pipelines that involve data collection, cleaning, transformation, and feature engineering to prepare data for AI/ML models.

Distributed Model Training: Managing the distributed training of AI models across multiple computing nodes to handle large datasets and complex models efficiently.

Model Serving and Deployment: Automating the deployment of AI models into production environments, including the management of model versioning, scaling, and updates.

5.3 Scheduling Abstraction Layer and Proactive Python SDK

ProActive Python SDK is an open-source library that empowers users to interact with and manage PWS and PAIO directly from their Python scripts. This integration unlocks seamless programmatic control over complex workflows, boosting efficiency and flexibility in your data-driven processes. Recent advancements have introduced a highly intuitive, declarative syntax using Python decorators, which dramatically simplifies workflow definition.

Key features of the SDK include:

Declarative and Programmatic Workflow Creation: Define entire Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs) using simple `@job` and `@task` decorators, or build them programmatically for dynamic, complex scenarios.

Simplified Development: Enjoy the convenience of Python, a widely adopted and versatile language, for your workflow management tasks. The SDK abstracts away complex low-level API interactions.

Resource Control and Monitoring: Take command of resources managed by the ProActive Resource Manager. Allocate, release, and monitor resources programmatically—including real-time hardware metrics like CPU and RAM usage—to ensure optimal performance.

Extensibility: Develop custom Python modules to leverage the full potential of ProActive. Integrate automation logic, custom task implementations, and tailored communication channels.

On-the-Fly Service Management: Programmatically deploy and undeploy external services (e.g., TensorBoard, MLOps dashboards) as part of your workflow, enabling a fully integrated analytics environment.

5.3.1 Modernizing Workflow Creation: The Declarative Approach

The latest versions of the ProActive Python SDK introduce decorators as the primary, recommended method for defining workflows. This approach makes the code more readable, more "Pythonic," and significantly reduces boilerplate compared to the programmatic approach.

Defining Workflows with Decorators (@job, @task)

You can define an entire workflow by decorating standard Python functions. The @job decorator defines the overall workflow, while the @task decorator converts a function into an executable task. Dependencies between tasks are automatically inferred from the function calls.

Listing: Creating a workflow with decorators

```
# Import the ProActive decorators
from proactive.decorators import task, job

@task.python(name="virtualenv_task", virtual_env='{"requirements": ["requests==2.26.0"]}')
def print_virtualenv():
    # This Python code will be executed as a ProActive task
    return ""

import requests
print("Running a simple http datetime request")
r = requests.get('http://httpbin.org/ip')
print(r.json())
"""

# Define the workflow using the @job decorator
@job(name="demo_decorators_virtualenv")
def workflow():
    # Calling the task function establishes it as part of the job
    print_virtualenv()

# To run the job (assuming a gateway is connected):
# gateway.submit(workflow)
```

In this example, @task.python creates a Python task and even specifies a virtual environment with required packages. The @job decorator packages the workflow function, and the call to print_virtualenv() inside it adds the task to the job.

Advanced Control Flow with Decorators

The SDK provides decorators for common control flow patterns, allowing you to build complex logic directly within your workflow definition.

@loop: Creates a loop to execute a set of tasks iteratively.

@branch: Implements if/else logic, allowing the workflow to proceed down different paths based on the outcome of a task.

@replicate: Executes the same task multiple times in parallel, often with different parameters.

These decorators simplify what would otherwise require complex programmatic logic and dependency management.

Enhanced Resource and Service Management

Real-time Resource Monitoring

The SDK now provides direct access to resource monitoring data, allowing you to make informed decisions about where to run your tasks. You can programmatically fetch hardware metrics from available nodes.

Listing: Fetching hardware metrics

```
from proactive import getProActiveGateway
from proactive.monitoring.ProactiveNodeMBeanClient import CPUMetric

# Connect to ProActive server
gateway = getProActiveGateway()
monitoring_client = gateway.getProactiveMonitoringClient()

# Retrieve and print current CPU metrics from available nodes
print("*\nDetailed CPU Usage:")
user_cpu = monitoring_client.get_cpu_metrics(CPUMetric.USER)
system_cpu = monitoring_client.get_cpu_metrics(CPUMetric.SYSTEM)
idle_cpu = monitoring_client.get_cpu_metrics(CPUMetric.IDLE)
wait_cpu = monitoring_client.get_cpu_metrics(CPUMetric.WAIT)

print(f"User CPU..... {user_cpu:.1f}%")
print(f"System CPU..... {system_cpu:.1f}%")
print(f"Idle CPU..... {idle_cpu:.1f}%")
print(f"Wait CPU..... {wait_cpu:.1f}%")

# gateway.close()
```

This capability is crucial for implementing dynamic resource allocation strategies, ensuring workloads are assigned to nodes with sufficient capacity.

Dynamic Service Deployment

The SDK includes methods to manage ProActive Services, allowing for the on-the-fly deployment and undeployment of tools like TensorBoard for real-time visualization or custom ML model-serving endpoints. This is facilitated through methods like `startService()` and `finishService()`, which can be called directly from your Python script to manage the lifecycle of these external services as part of your workflow.

5.3.2 Programmatic Workflow Construction

While decorators are the recommended approach, the SDK retains its powerful programmatic API for scenarios requiring dynamic workflow generation at runtime. This method provides fine-grained control over every aspect of the job and its tasks.

Getting Started with the ProActive Python SDK

Here is a guide to help you get started with the programmatic approach:

1. Prerequisites

- Have access to the ProActive Scheduler (trial or private)
- Java SDK LTS (works with Java 8, 11 and 13)
- Python 3.6 or later

2. Create a Virtual Environment (Optional but Recommended)

```
python3 -m venv env

# On Mac/Linux :
source env/bin/activate

# On Windows:
# env\Scripts\activate
```

3. Install/Upgrade Required Packages

```
python3 -m pip install --upgrade pip setuptools python-dotenv proactive
```

4. Usage Example (Programmatic)

This example demonstrates connecting to a server, creating a job, adding a Python task, and submitting it.

Listing: Connecting to a ProActive server and creating a job

```
import getpass
from proactive import ProActiveGateway

proactive_url = "https://try.activeeon.com:8443"
print(f"Connecting to {proactive_url}...")
gateway = ProActiveGateway(proactive_url)

# Securely input your credentials
gateway.connect(username=input("Username: "), password=getpass.getpass("Password: "))
assert gateway.isConnected(), "Failed to connect to the ProActive server!"

# Create a ProActive job
print("Creating a ProActive job...")
job = gateway.createJob("SimpleJob")

# Create a ProActive task
print("Creating a ProActive Python task...")
task = gateway.createPythonTask("SimplePythonTask")
task.setTaskImplementation('print("Hello from ProActive!)"')
task.addGenericInformation("PYTHON_COMMAND", "python3")

# Add the Python task to the job
job.addTask(task)

# Job submission
job_id = gateway.submitJob(job)
print(f"Job submitted with ID: {job_id}")

# Retrieve job output
print("Job output:")
print(gateway.getJobOutput(job_id))

# Cleanup
gateway.close()
print("Disconnected and finished.")
```

Supported Programming Languages

The ProActive Python SDK supports a wide range of programming languages for task execution within the ProActive Scheduler environment. These supported languages include bash, cmd, docker-compose, scalaw, groovy, javascript, python, cpython, ruby, perl, R, and powershell.

Task Dependencies

To manage task dependencies programmatically, you can use the addDependency method.

Listing: Creating a task dependency

```
# Create a ProActive job
job = gateway.createJob("Simple_Dependency_Demo")
# Create the first task (Task A)
task_A = gateway.createPythonTask("Task_A")
task_A.setTaskImplementation('print("Task A is running)")')
# Create the second task (Task B) which depends on Task A
task_B = gateway.createPythonTask("Task_B")
task_B.setTaskImplementation('print("Task B is running)")')
task_B.addDependency(task_A)
# Add tasks to the job
job.addTask(task_A)
job.addTask(task_B)
# Submit the job
job_id = gateway.submitJob(job)
print(f"Job submitted with ID: {job_id}")
```

In this example, Task B will only start after Task A has been successfully completed.

5.3.3 Workflow Data Management

Efficient data management is pivotal in executing distributed tasks. This encompasses handling input/output files and managing data flow between tasks.

Workflow Data Spaces

Workflow Data Spaces refer to designated storage areas within the ProActive Scheduler's environment: the "User Space" and the "Global Space."

User Space: A private storage area accessible only to the user's jobs.

Global Space: A shared storage space accessible by all users.

You can transfer files to and from these spaces using `userspaceapi` and `globalspaceapi` within a task's implementation.

Uploading and Downloading Files

In contrast to Data Spaces, you may need to transfer files directly between your local machine and the task's execution environment. This is facilitated by two key methods on the task object:

`addInputFile(path)`: Uploads files from your local machine to the task's local space before execution.

`addOutputFile(path)`: Downloads files from the task's local space back to your local machine after execution.

Note that the `@task` decorator also provides `input_folder` and `output_folder` parameters for a more integrated way of handling file transfers in a declarative workflow.

5.3.4 DEKO Use Case (UC5)

The implementation described here serves as an exemplary application of Use Case 5, aimed at binary classification for failure prediction within a manufacturing setup. The specified workflow encapsulates a sequence of tasks integral to the ML training pipeline, which includes data preprocessing, model training, and validation. The primary objective is to forecast potential failures, thereby facilitating preemptive actions to mitigate downtime and enhance production efficiency.

Implementation Overview

This example delineates the workflow for a specific subset within the manufacturing domain, focusing on IDEKO's scenario. The implementation journey begins with the setup of the ProActive Python SDK environment. Following this, the ProActive gateway is established, creating a conduit for executing the predefined ML workflow on the ProActive Scheduler. While the example below uses the programmatic approach, it is important to note that this entire workflow could be expressed more concisely using the new decorator syntax.

Listing: UC5 example setup (programmatic approach)

```
# ... (imports and gateway connection) ...
job = create_job(gateway, "IDEKO")
fork_env = create_fork_env(gateway, job)
# ...
read_data_task = create_python_task(gateway, "read_data", ...)
add_padding_task = create_python_task(gateway, "add_padding", ..., dependencies=[read_data_task])
split_data_task = create_python_task(gateway, "split_data", ..., dependencies=[add_padding_task])
train_nn = create_python_task(gateway, "train_nn", ..., dependencies=[split_data_task])
# ... (add tasks to job and submit) ...
```

Workflow Specification

The workflow is articulated through a series of sequential tasks:

- Data Reading (`read_data`): Ingests the dataset.
- Data Preprocessing (`add_padding`): Applies necessary transformations.
- Data Splitting (`split_data`): Partitions data into training and test sets.
- Model Training (`train_nn`): Trains the neural network model.

Each task's dependency is meticulously managed to ensure the correct execution sequence. This use case exemplifies the application of the ProActive Python SDK in operationalizing ML workflows, showcasing a streamlined process from data ingestion to model training.

5.4 Recent Advancements and Future Roadmap

The ProActive platform is under continuous development, with a focus on enhancing the capabilities and user experience of the Python SDK to meet the evolving needs of the ExtremeXP project and the broader scientific computing community.

Recent Advancements

Significant progress has been made in extending the ProActive Python SDK to empower users and partners. The key results from the recent development cycle include:

Declarative Workflows with Decorators: The successful implementation of `@task` and `@job` decorators have fundamentally simplified workflow creation, improving code readability and maintainability. Advanced control flow decorators (`@branch`, `@loop`, `@replicate`) have also been added.

Resource Monitoring: An initial version of a resource monitoring client has been completed, providing programmatic access to real-time hardware metrics like CPU and RAM usage, enabling more intelligent task scheduling.

On-the-Fly Container Builds: Support has been added for building container images from Dockerfiles on-the-fly as part of a workflow.

Service Management: The SDK now includes methods to programmatically manage the lifecycle of ProActive Services, allowing for the dynamic deployment of necessary tools.

Future Roadmap

The development focus for the upcoming period will be on extending these new capabilities and further optimizing the platform for complex AI/ML workloads.

Enhanced DAG Decorators: Functionality for decorators will be expanded with additional features and more advanced examples to further improve ease of use.

Advanced Resource Monitoring: The resource monitoring framework will be enhanced to include GPU metrics and other hardware-specific information, addressing key requirements for optimizing resource tracking and selection within ExtremeXP.

Expanded Service Management: The on-demand deployment of AI tools will be a primary focus, tailored to ExtremeXP needs. This includes seamless integration with tools like TensorBoard for real-time metrics visualization and the ActiveEon MLOps Dashboard for streamlined model deployment, serving, and monitoring.

These advancements pave the way for a future where advanced analytics and machine learning are more accessible and efficiently managed, ensuring competitiveness and innovation in the industrial and scientific landscape.

6 Context-aware Access Control for Experiment-driven Analytics

The ExtremeXP Access Control system is designed to provide robust protection for any **Resource**, meaning any backend services and data files which can be accessed through a HTTP link, safeguarding them from malicious user actions. It utilizes Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC), following the eXtensible Access Control Markup Language (XACML) standard, to manage user permissions. This approach, which differs from the more common Role-Based Access Control (RBAC), considers the context of each user, making the access control mechanism more modular and dynamic.

In the scenario of ExtremeXP, access control must be decentralized to enable multiple organizations to conduct experiments using shared databases, ensuring traceability, accountability, privacy, and security. To achieve this, ExtremeXP's Access Control system is based on blockchain, a type of Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) that can store data and execute code segments known as Smart Contracts on a distributed platform.

ExtremeXP establishes its protection policies on the blockchain by using Smart Contracts as the foundation for these policies. The system also utilizes on-chain data storage to retain the essential context required to verify user access permissions. This approach creates immutable records on the blockchain, ensuring traceability for future auditing purposes. The designed architecture was introduced in D2.1. Below, we present the relevant technologies used in the components of the access control mechanism.

6.1 Technologies used in the Implementation

6.1.1 MetaMask

MetaMask [MetaMask2024] is a web wallet that operates on blockchain networks, allowing users to approve transactions, transfer assets, and validate Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs). In addition, MetaMask enables users to store NFTs and connect with aggregation services. As the most widely used web and mobile wallet, it allows users to interact seamlessly with decentralized applications. The wallet includes various components, such as a Software Development Kit (SDK) and an Application Programming Interface (API), which facilitate the development of new features and the integration of applications with MetaMask.

6.1.2 Keycloak

Keycloak [Keycloak2024] is an open-source access management solution that provides authentication and authorization services, backed by a large community and comprehensive documentation. It allows for fine-grained authorization policies, including Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) and Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) mechanisms. Keycloak can be extended with custom plugins, facilitating integration with Ethereum, through libraries such as Web3j. Additionally, Keycloak supports security protocols like OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect standards, ensuring compatibility with other systems and components within the ExtremeXP framework. These features make Keycloak an ideal choice for developing the ExtremeXP access control system in a decentralized model.

6.1.3 Hyperledger Besu

Hyperledger Besu [Hyperledger2024] is an open-source Ethereum client developed as part of the Linux Foundation's Decentralized Trust (LFDT) project. It meets the requirements for a permissioned blockchain network, while also supporting Ethereum's standard features, such as smart contracts and NFTs. Hyperledger Besu supports various consensus mechanisms tailored to different needs, including Proof of Authority (PoA) protocols such as IBFT 2.0, QBFT, and Clique, as well as Proof of Stake. In the context of ExtremeXP, the group of interconnected Hyperledger Besu nodes collaborating is referred to as the ExtremeXP Blockchain Network.

Additionally, Hyperledger Besu closes its blocks at a predefined interval, typically one second, which adds predictability to transaction processing times. These features make Hyperledger Besu an excellent platform for decentralized access control, combining the flexibility of policy implementation through smart contracts with the reliability of its constant block closing time.

6.2 ExtremeXP Access Control System Architecture

The ExtremeXP Access Control Architecture divides management and control into two distinct modules.

The first module, known as the **Access Control Interface**, manages all tasks related to data assets access protection and security, including user registration, authentication, attribute configuration, protection policy management, blockchain integration, and a single sign-on (SSO) service. This module facilitates the integration of blockchain smart contract policies with the business rules of the ExtremeXP project. It also manages the logic to bridge users from the Web2 application to the Web3 environment. It consists of three layers:

1. a REST API at the front for integration,
2. a User Management layer that connects the Access Control Interface with the Keycloak system, and
3. a Blockchain Interface for deploying new policies and creating wallets on the blockchain.

These layers streamline the integration of ExtremeXP modules with Keycloak and Hyperledger Besu.

The second module, known as the **Access Control Proxy**, is responsible for resource protection. It intercepts every request to backend services and verifies the user's permissions. Since the ExtremeXP Access Control policies are Smart Contracts on the blockchain, this module can operate in a decentralized manner, creating the bridge between Web2 and Web3.

Figure 18 ExtremeXP Access Control Architecture.

On a technical level, these two modules are deployed using GitHub Actions to create public Docker images. These Docker images can be used to set up the architecture outlined in Figure 18. The Access Control Interface is represented by the blue box, and the Access Control Proxy is displayed as a red box. Also, the figure shows that all services are behind a Nginx proxy, with Docker Compose as the orchestrator for all services. Docker Compose is a tool for defining and running multi-container Docker applications, allowing for easy deployment, and scaling of the system. All the module details are presented in further sections. The flow illustrated in Figure 18 outlines a sequential series of actions for authentication and authorization, which are further detailed in the following sections.

A key aspect of the ExtremeXP Access Control Architecture is that each organization participating in ExtremeXP has its own instance of Keycloak and a node of Hyperledger Besu. This means that for every organization, there is a one-to-one relationship between its Keycloak instance and its blockchain node. As a result, each organization can manage its users independently, defining roles, groups, attributes, and more. Additionally, the Hyperledger Besu node connects to the ExtremeXP Blockchain Network, enabling policy enforcement and collaboration. Furthermore, the organization Keycloak has a blockchain wallet that allows for signing and executing policies on the blockchain. Through the Keycloak wallet address, ExtremeXP Access Control can identify the source of a transaction.

6.2.1 Authentication Mechanism

Authentication is the process by which your identity is confirmed through a credential. For authentication, the user must have a registered account, which can be created through the ExtremeXP Portal using the Access Control Interface REST API. With the Access Control Interface REST API, systems can register new users, authenticate them, retrieve user data, and add user attributes. All these features compose the user management functions of the Access Control Interface. It is important to note that the same interfaces used to manage user attributes are also used in the context handler for policy enforcement.

In the context of ExtremeXP Access Control, the blockchain does not store users' credentials or any personally identifiable information (PII). Storing this information on the blockchain would create a permanent and unalterable record system, thus making compliance with GDPR challenging. Instead, ExtremeXP Access Control employs pseudo-anonymity, by registering only a Universally Unique Identifier (UUID) to track user actions. In contrast, most user attributes are maintained off-chain in the Keycloak database.

The authentication flow involves a series of straightforward steps. Initially,

1. The user logs in via the frontend portal.
2. Secondly, the Access Control Interface authenticates the user against the organization's Keycloak system. If the user is already registered and the provided credentials are valid, the organization's Keycloak issues a JSON Web Token (JWT) access token.
3. Finally, this JWT token is securely delivered to the user through the frontend portal.

All other user-related processes, including registration and user information management, follow the same procedure, differing only in the specific input and output data. From this point forward, the frontend application must include the token in all requests to prevent an access denied response.

6.2.2 Authorization Mechanism

Authorization is the process of allowing a user to have access to a **Resource** or perform specific actions in a computer system. In Figure 18, the diagram illustrates the process of granting or denying access to a **Resource** (any backend services and data files). Initially, it is assumed that the user possesses a JWT token obtained from the authentication process. The first step involves the user requesting a resource, which is then intercepted by the proxy (step 3). The Access Control Proxy forwards the user's request to the Keycloak authorization mechanism (step 4), along with some contextual information.

Keycloak checks whether the requested resource has a protection policy associated with it. If it is not protected, authorization is granted. However, if there are policies related to the request, Keycloak forwards it for evaluation against the access control policies defined in smart contracts (step 5). A series of smart contracts assess the policies and generate an event containing the result once the transaction is complete.

Meanwhile, Keycloak continues to wait for the transaction conclusion by checking its status on the blockchain until the transaction is completed. After the transaction result is available, Keycloak returns the result for the proxy. Finally, if the evaluation returns a grant access response, then the user will have access to the resource (step 6).

In this process, it is important to highlight three key points. First, from the user's perspective, the Access Control Proxy is invisible. If the user has the necessary access, the request will successfully return the resource. If access is denied, the proxy provides an error message as feedback.

Second, the Access Control Proxy is location-agnostic; since the access policy is stored on the blockchain, the proxy's physical location or redundancy does not impact its function. This feature enhances the system's fault tolerance, as multiple instances can connect to redundant Keycloak instances. Additionally, since the proxy operates behind NginX, it can effectively scale with load balancing and redundancy when properly configured, increasing the solution's robustness.

Third, since policy enforcement on the blockchain is managed by the organization Keycloak, all policies are executed by Keycloak on behalf of the user. To ensure users are held accountable for their actions within the ExtremeXP system, the ExtremeXP Access Control incorporates a smart contract that records the user's authorization for Keycloak to act on their behalf.

Figure 19. ExtremeXP Access Control OnBehalfOf transaction flow.

In Figure 19, the process for user wallet registration and authorization within an organization's Keycloak begins when the Access Control Interface registers a new user (step 1). Upon successful registration (step 2), a new wallet is created for the user on the ExtremeXP Blockchain Network (step 3). The wallet is created and linked to the user (step 4). Finally, using the user's identification along with the newly created wallet address, the Access Control Interface sets the wallet address as part of the user's attributes on the organization Keycloak. After registration, the user must save the returned wallet private key in MetaMask to be able to sign the OnBehalfOf authorization transaction (step 5). After the correct MetaMask configuration, the frontend application can now request the user to sign the OnBehalfOf authorization transaction (step 6). After the user signs the transaction, the portal receives the transaction confirmation (step 7).

The OnBehalfOf smart contract stores the user's wallet address, the organization's Keycloak wallet address, and a timestamp that is valid for 24 hours. During every execution of a protection policy, the blockchain smart contracts first check whether the organization's Keycloak instance,

which signed the policy enforcement transaction, has permission from the user to act on their behalf by consulting the OnBehalfOf smart contract. If the organization's Keycloak has the necessary permissions and the authorization has not expired, the policy will be executed as intended. If the permissions are not granted or have expired, the policy smart contract will emit a "denied" event by default.

Figure 20 demonstrates how Keycloak associates a resource with a policy of enforcement, as detailed in steps 3, 4, and 5 of Figure 18. The organization manager must provide the resource name and URI of the resource to be protected (steps 1 and 2), along with the allowed action referred to as a Scope (step 3). Further, the manager inputs the policy smart contract address that needs to be enforced in this particular context during the request evaluation process (Figure 18, step 4). It is worth noticing that the policy address in the ExtremeXP Blockchain Network is informed on the policy deployment through the Access Control Interface (Figure 18, step 6). After the deployment, the address can also be consulted using the Access Control Interface REST API.

In Figure 18, when a request arrives at the proxy, the proxy checks the resource (or URI) against the list of resources managed by Keycloak. If the resource is registered for protection, as shown in Figure 12, the proxy assembles the request context and forwards it to Keycloak for evaluation (Figure 18, step 4). At the organization Keycloak, the blockchain plugin processes the evaluation request and creates a transaction on the blockchain (Figure 18, step 5) based on the policy specified in the Resource Attribute (as illustrated in Figure 18 point 4). Also, if the resource is not listed for protection, the proxy will forward the request without evaluating it.

Clients > Client details > Resource details

/exp/projects/Yago%20Rezende-Test-1739331823/datasets

Action

Owner accesscontrol

Name * /exp/projects/Yago%20Rezende-Test-1739331823/datasets **1**

Display name datasets

Type

URIs

[+ Add URI](#)

Authorization scopes

Icon URI

User-Managed access enabled Off

Resource attribute

Key	Value
policy	0x6eD3FF683dff8A46aBA5C ... 4

[+ Add an attribute](#)

[Save](#) [Cancel](#)

Figure 20 Registering a resource for protection on Keycloak.

6.2.3 Hyperledger Besu Network and Policy Enforcement Smart Contracts

The permissioned Hyperledger Besu network deployed in ExtremeXP is designed to enforce access control policies and consists of four nodes capable of sending and validating

transactions. Those transactions are to enforce policies in smart contracts, which are developed following the XACML ABAC standards using Solidity, a domain-specific language (DSL) for Ethereum.

The design structures smart contracts in two groups: policy points, and contracts with use case rules called RulesContracts.

The design structures smart contracts in two groups: policy points, and the RulesContracts. The set of policy points for smart contracts are Policy Decision Point (PDP), Policy Administration Point (PAP), and Policy Information Point (PIP). Furthermore, there is a dedicated RulesContract for each of the five use cases: Ideko, CS, I2CAT, Airbus and Moby.

The policy points and RulesContracts smart contracts act together to decide whether to allow or deny access to a resource and return the result to the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP). In this scenario, the PEP is composed of Keycloak and proxy.

The resource contains a URI for accessing the resource, but this URI is also the resource identifier known as the resource ID. Moreover, the identifier must be protected, and users should only have access to this resource if the set of policies allows access

Data processors are users of the ExtremeXP framework, and they are typically employees of a company that hosts the project's use cases. Therefore, each company will host a blockchain node on the ExtremeXP Blockchain Network, and all the requests will be sent by these nodes on behalf of the employees using account abstraction. Account abstraction is an Ethereum feature developed and standardized through ERC-4337, which allows smart contracts to sign and approve transactions on behalf of the user. The ERC-4337 enables the creation of user accounts within the smart contract and enables it to sign transactions on behalf of the user [ERC]. It is important for ExtremeXP because the data processor cannot access the blockchain.

6.2.3.1 Policy Enforcement

First, once the request described in section 6.2.2 reaches the Policy Enforcement Point (PEP), the user waits for the enforcement decision, and the PEP sends the request to the blockchain for evaluation.

Second, inside the blockchain, the request is sent to the PDP smart contract, which gets from PAP the RulesContract address that protects the resource related to the request.

Third, the PAP has a mapping of all the protected Resource IDs associated with their respective RulesContract Addresses. The PAP makes a delegate call to the RulesContract.

Fourth, the RulesContract has the logical operation of rules tailored by each use case. The contract receives the data from the request and evaluates access based on the rules in the policy defined for that resource ID. Thus, the RulesContract sends the result to the PAP smart contract.

Fifth, although RulesContract has a set of rules for the resource, some contextual attributes cannot be handled by the blockchain or are not provided by Keycloak. Those contextual attributes must be managed by a trusted source, which manages them off-chain and sends them to the PIP smart contract.

Sixth, PIP receives the contextual attributes the trusted source provides, such as geolocation and time shift. Once the PIP has that data, it is sent to the PAP. Seventh, the PAP redirects the information received from the RulesContract and the PIP and delivers it to the PDP, which makes the decision based on the RulesContract computation and the information provided by the PIP. Finally, the PDP evaluates the access requested and emits the decision event as a transaction on a valid block; the “company node” reads it and returns the decision to the PEP.

The policies were first defined and then implemented on smart contracts to enforce rules for resources per use case. Table 3 presents the rules of the policies applied for each use case before transforming the rules into smart contracts.

Table 3 Policy rules.

Index	Rule	Description	Attribute	Use Case
1	$(\text{Lat and Long}) \subset \text{expected area (premises)}$	User is within allowed location	Lat and Long	CS, I2CAT, MOBY, IDEKO, AIRBUS
2	$\text{IP} \in \text{to whitelist}$	User se accessing with an allowed IP	IP provided by company or VPN IP	CS, I2CAT, MOBY, IDEKO, AIRBUS
3	$\text{User ID} \in \text{to the team}$	Personnel belongs to staff	Credential	CS, I2CAT, MOBY, IDEKO, AIRBUS
4	$\text{StartShift} < \text{Request timestamp} < \text{EndShift}$	The user is requesting access to the data within allowed work shift	Timestamp	CS, I2CAT. MOBY, IDEKO, AIRBUS
5	$\text{Connection Protocol} = \text{HTTPS}$	The access control component only accepts requests which is using HTTPS	Logical	CS, I2CAT, MOBY, IDEKO, AIRBUS
6	$\text{Day} \in \{\text{weekdays}\}$	The request should be within weekly days	Timestamp	I2CAT, MOBY, AIRBUS
7	$(\text{Lat and Long}) \subset \{\text{country}\}$	The end user has to be in the allowed country	Lat x Long	CS
8	$\text{UserID} \in \{\text{special permission}\}$	User is enabled to act in the system	Logical (true or false)	CS
9	$\text{Expected hash of the file} = \text{the Last version of the document hashed}$	The hash provided in the request is equal to the last version of the document hash	Hash	I2CAT, MOBY

10	<u>Hash of workflow provided by requester = Stored hash</u>	<u>The hash provided on the request should be equal</u>	Hash	MOBY, I2CAT,
11	<u>Resource Signatures ≥ 2 by expected users</u>	<u>The resource must be signed by at least two validators to be available for use.</u>	Hash of Signatures	I2CAT
12	<u>Hash of DPA¹ provided = Hash stored by the Company</u>	The request must prove the persistent agreement between the parties through the hash.	Hash	CS, I2CAT, Moby. AIRBUS
13	<u>USER has Role</u>	The user has a registered role provided by the admin	Logical	CS, I2CAT, MOBY, AIRBUS, IDEKO
14	Data anonymised= true	End-user data should be anonymized before it is available	Logical	I2CAT
15	<u>Workflow hash = \subset {Expected Workflow hash}</u>	The Workflow is persistent and accepted by the data owner during the sharing agreement.	Hash	IDEKO

Figure 21 and Figure 22 illustrate how the rules are applied to smart contracts. In the *RulesContract*, when a request is received, the contract executes each rule based on the parameters provided in the request. It handles the request using functions such as

isIPWhitelisted and *isUserNearApprovedLocation*. The *RulesContract* then compiles the results from these functions and returns the result to the PAP.

```
function isIPWhitelisted(string memory ip↑, bytes32[] memory allowedIPHashes↑) public pure returns (bool) {
    bytes32 ipHash = keccak256(abi.encodePacked(ip↑));
    for (uint i = 0; i < allowedIPHashes↑.length; i++) {
        if (allowedIPHashes↑[i] == ipHash) {
            return true;
        }
    }
    return false;
}
```

Figure 21. Rule for IP in smart contract.

```
function isUserNearApprovedLocation(
    int256 userLat↑,
    int256 userLon↑,
    Location[] memory allowedLocations↑,
    uint256 radiusMeters↑
) public pure returns (bool) {
    for (uint i = 0; i < allowedLocations↑.length; i++) {
        Location memory loc = allowedLocations↑[i];
        if (isWithinRadius(userLat↑, userLon↑, loc.lat, loc.longi, radiusMeters↑)) {
            return true;
        }
    }
    return false;
}
```

Figure 22. Rule for location in smart contract.

7 Decentralized Data Management

7.1 Approach

The ExtremeXP Decentralized Data Management (DDM) system provides a robust foundation for handling heterogeneous data and metadata assets across the project’s distributed modules. Designed to support varying storage and access requirements among machines operating in diverse geographic and operational environments, the system ensures scalable, low-latency data handling through a decentralized architecture built on Zenoh¹².

It incorporates various advanced functionalities, besides the storage and querying of data artefacts. DDM provides automated metadata extraction and enrichment at the time of data ingestion, combining structural analysis with large language model (LLM) assistance to enhance discoverability and semantic alignment. The DDM dataset catalog maintains unified indexing across data domains, while files and their associated metadata are stored in decentralized manner using Zenoh’s file systems abstraction, object stores and timeseries stores, depending on the context and requirements of each module.

Crucially, the system integrates mechanisms for verifiable data provenance and sharing through NFT-backed identifiers (developed as part of Task 2.3). This enables traceable ownership, trusted audit trails, and support for expectation-driven dataset rewards. These features foster secure, flexible, and interoperable data exchange across the ExtremeXP ecosystem.

7.2 DDM Architecture

The architecture illustrated in the figure below represents the core of the decentralized data management system developed under Task 5.5 of the ExtremeXP project.

Figure 23 DDM Architecture

¹² <https://zenoh.io/>

At the frontend of this architecture lies a **React**¹³-based **user interface**, which acts as the primary access point for users across various roles (e.g., data providers, evaluators, and consumers). Users interact with the platform via the React application running in their browsers. Requests from the UI, such as uploading files, triggering metadata generation, or browsing catalog contents, are routed through the **NGINX**¹⁴ **web server**, which serves static frontend assets and securely proxies API calls to the backend.

The backend itself is built on **Flask**¹⁵, running behind **Gunicorn**¹⁶ as a Web Server Gateway Interface (WSGI) application server. It handles API requests and orchestrates interactions with both the Zenoh decentralized storage infrastructure and the background processing system. Whenever operations are too compute-intensive or time-consuming, such as file parsing, LLM-powered metadata generation, or expectation validation, they are offloaded to a **message broker** (can be configured in .env file to invoke Redis or PostgreSQL, PostgreSQL is used in the current version), which feeds a distributed **Celery**¹⁷-based **task queue**. The task workers, running independently, fetch jobs from the broker and write results to PostgreSQL and the Zenoh P2P Network.

File and data storage in the architecture are handled through the **Zenoh P2P Network**. Zenoh enables a decentralized model, where each peer can rely on different type of storage technologies, such as **MinIO**¹⁸ **S3-compatible storage**, Linux **file systems**, or **InfluxDB**¹⁹ for time-series data. This flexible setup allows each ExtremeXP module or participant to tailor data persistence to its local infrastructure and performance needs, while remaining part of a synchronized and decentralized ecosystem.

On the right part of the diagram, a dedicated “Services” module shows the various functional components powered by Celery tasks:

- **Ollama**²⁰ **LLM Service**: Used for generating descriptive metadata from unstructured content using local large language models.
- **Metadata Generation** and **Dataset Report Generation**: Services that parse, analyze, and summarize data assets based on domain needs.
- **Expectation Suite Generation/Validation**: These modules allow stakeholders to define and enforce expectations (quality constraints) over datasets.
- **Smart Contracts Deployment and Transactions**: Manages the actual interaction with the blockchain, recording data operations immutably.

The DDM system, as part of the ExtremeXP project, was integrated with Web3 capabilities. The system utilizes **Infura**²¹ with **Metamask**²² as a Web3 provider in order to connect to the **Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM)** network. This integration allows the backend as well as the frontend to interact with smart contracts deployed on the blockchain using web3 Python and JavaScript libraries, respectively. These contracts govern actions, such as minting **NFTs** to represent data assets, logging access and usage, enabling tokenized rewards for data sharing. Smart contract

¹³ <https://react.dev/>

¹⁴ <https://nginx.org/>

¹⁵ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/stable/>

¹⁶ <https://gunicorn.org/>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/celery/celery>

¹⁸ <https://min.io/>

¹⁹ <https://www.influxdata.com/>

²⁰ <https://ollama.com/>

²¹ <https://www.infura.io/>

²² <https://metamask.io/>

execution is part of the asynchronous task queue and tied to the provenance and incentive mechanisms central to ExtremeXP's vision.

The decentralized data management, described above allows data to be stored close to where it is generated or needed, provides transparency and provenance through blockchain integration, while supporting complex chained task execution via an event-driven backend.\

7.3 Components Description & Functionality

7.3.1 Zenoh P2P Network

Zenoh constitutes the core data transport and storage module in the decentralized architecture of ExtremeXP. It enables peer-to-peer (P2P) data synchronization, semantic discovery, and location-transparent access to heterogeneous data assets distributed across the nodes of the Zenoh network. Zenoh not only facilitates low-latency communication and content-based routing but also abstracts the complexity of distributed systems.

7.3.1.1 Storage Backends

Zenoh allows different nodes in the network to use their own storage technology, while still making data accessible in a unified way. For example, one node may use MinIO for object storage, another one can rely on a local file system, and a third one may store time-series data in InfluxDB. Data can be published, discovered, and queried regardless of the backend store infrastructure of each node.

7.3.1.2 Protocol and QoS Features

Through Zenoh, we can unify publish/subscribe, query/reply, and store/replicate paradigms into a single coherent protocol stack. Zenoh routers can discover peers automatically using multicast or specific peer configurations. Moreover, Zenoh's admin space offers configuration options regarding replication mechanisms, allowing peers to replicate only the configured subset of a keyspace, optimizing resource usage.

7.3.2 DDM Backend Application

7.3.2.1 Overview

The backend of the ExtremeXP Decentralized Data Management system is built in a modular way using Flask and is served via Gunicorn. The application layer exposes a RESTful API consumed by the React frontend and external clients.

The backend handles multiple responsibilities:

- **Request Routing:** It handles API calls related to file uploads, metadata submission, catalog exploration, expectation management, and user interactions.
- **Celery Task Orchestration:** For operations that require asynchronous processing, such as file chunks merging, LLM-based metadata generation, or blockchain transaction submission, the application interfaces with the Celery-based task queue via a message broker (Redis or PostgreSQL).
- **Persistent Storage:** The application acts as a mediator to the Zenoh P2P network, enabling decentralized persistent file storage, while abstracting backend specific implementations (e.g., S3, filesystem, InfluxDB).
- **Data Catalog:** The backend reads from and writes PostgreSQL database, which serves as the authoritative catalog for data and metadata assets, provenance logs, and task states.
- **Authentication and Authorization:** User authentication and authorization are handled through authentication and authorization services built on Keycloak, which manages

identity federation, access control, and session lifecycle using OAuth2 and OpenID Connect protocols.

- **Web3 Integration:** The system integrates Web3 features for interacting with smart contracts deployed on Ethereum-compatible networks. These interactions include compiling and deploying contracts, verifying asset ownership, asserting data quality, and managing token-based reward mechanisms. Web3 interactions are managed via providers like Infura, and actions are initiated from the backend or via Celery tasks depending on context and workload.

7.3.2.2 APIs and Swagger Documentation

The exposed API is fully documented using OpenAPI (Swagger²³), as shown in the interface below. Based on the Swagger documentation, the ExtremeXP Decentralized Data Management API is designed with a modular RESTful architecture that organizes its endpoints into clearly defined functional groups under specific relevant namespaces.

Figure 24 DDM Swagger Grouped Namespaces.

- The **file** and **files** groups of the API endpoints support robust and flexible file management within the ExtremeXP decentralized data management platform. The endpoints under these namespaces are integrated with Zenoh P2P network and the asynchronous Celery task orchestration system, enabling upload, update, retrieval, and deletion of both individual and bulk data assets.

²³ <https://editor.swagger.io/>

file		File-related operations	^
PATCH	/ddm/file/update/{file_id}	Update project_id, description, use_case, filename	▼ 🔒
POST	/ddm/file/upload	Upload a file with optional metadata and store in Zenoh, then start metadata processing task	▼ 🔒
POST	/ddm/file/upload-link	Retrieve file from URL and start Celery processing	▼ 🔒
POST	/ddm/file/upload/async	Upload a file asynchronously in chunks and store directly in Zenoh	▼ 🔒
GET	/ddm/file/{file_id}	Download a file	▼ 🔒
DELETE	/ddm/file/{file_id}/delete	Soft delete a file and remove it from Zenoh if no metadata remains	▼ 🔒
files		Multiple File-related operations	^
DELETE	/ddm/files/delete	Delete multiple files with Zenoh cleanup and metadata handling	▼ 🔒
POST	/ddm/files/download	Download multiple files as a ZIP archive (Fetched from Zenoh)	▼ 🔒
POST	/ddm/files/download/project	Download all files under a given project path as a ZIP archive	▼ 🔒
PATCH	/ddm/files/update	Update multiple files	▼ 🔒
POST	/ddm/files/upload	Upload multiple files with metadata, store in Zenoh, and start processing tasks	▼ 🔒
POST	/ddm/files/upload-links	Retrieve multiple files from URLs and start Celery processing	▼ 🔒

Figure 25 DDM Swagger /file & /files namespaces.

The API supports the three following distinct mechanisms for file upload.

- **Standard Upload** (POST /ddm/file/upload)

This endpoint allows users to upload a file or many files directly with optional metadata. The uploaded files are immediately stored in Zenoh, and metadata extraction or processing tasks (e.g., file analysis, LLM-assisted enrichment) are automatically queued for execution by Celery Workers. This method suits typical frontend interactions where metadata is available at the time of submission.
- **Upload from URL** (POST /ddm/file/upload-link)

For remote resources, this endpoint fetches a file directly from a given URL and stores it in Zenoh. Once downloaded, the backend initiates the same background processing pipeline as the direct upload. This method is useful for ingesting externally hosted datasets without requiring the user to download and reupload manually.
- **Asynchronous Chunked Upload** (POST /ddm/file/upload/async)

Designed for large files, this endpoint allows asynchronous uploading in multiple chunks. When the backend receives all chunks, it initiates the same background processing pipeline as the direct upload, with an additional initial step to merge the chunks into a complete file.

These upload methods are complemented by appropriate endpoints to **update** (PATCH), **download** (GET), or **delete** (DELETE) individual files (/ddm/file/{file_id}), as well as to manage simultaneously numerous files through the endpoint under /files namespace (e.g., POST /ddm/files/upload, POST /ddm/files/download, DELETE /ddm/files/delete). All these interactions are combined with log generation, ensuring traceability throughout the data lifecycle.

- The endpoints under **file metadata namespace** manage operations related to metadata handling. They support getting file metadata records by file Identifier and batch metadata retrieval via a list of file identifiers. Especially the /file_metadata/reports endpoint returns the generated profile report for a given dataset identifier in HTML format.

Figure 26 DDM Swagger /file_metadata namespace

- The endpoints under the **uploader_metadata** namespace support CRUD operations on the metadata uploaded by a user or service along with the file.

Figure 27 DDM Swagger /uploader_metadata namespace

- The endpoints under **catalog** namespace enable users to query the decentralized dataset catalog. All the GET endpoints include arguments to customize pagination, per-column filtering, and sorting, ensuring efficient querying across large data collections. The /tree endpoint returns files in a nested, directory-style JSON response. Especially, the /my-catalog endpoint returns a list of file records joined with the corresponding up-to-date usage and related web3 transaction logs.

catalog		File catalog operations	^
POST	/ddm/catalog/advanced	Supports complex JSON expressions for file filtering	↓ 🔒
GET	/ddm/catalog/list	Retrieve a paginated list of files with optional filters and sorting	↓ 🔒
GET	/ddm/catalog/my-catalog	Retrieve the catalog of files uploaded by the current user	↓ 🔒
GET	/ddm/catalog/options	Retrieve file options based on project ID, filename, or user ID	↓ 🔒
GET	/ddm/catalog/tree	Lazy-load tree data: paginated, filterable, sortable	↓

Figure 28 DDM Swagger /catalog namespace

- The endpoints under **expectations** namespace allow users to create new suites (/suites POST endpoint) and query existing ones (/suites GET endpoint). The last one involves appropriate arguments for filtering, sorting, and pagination. Additionally, users can upload a sample file by making a POST request to the /upload-sample endpoints, which then triggers an asynchronous task to generate necessary descriptive metadata for this file.

expectations		Operations related to expectations	^
GET	/ddm/expectations/suites	List all expectation suites with filters	↓ 🔒
POST	/ddm/expectations/suites	Post a new expectation suite	↓ 🔒
GET	/ddm/expectations/suites/{suite_id}	Get details of an expectation suite	↓ 🔒
POST	/ddm/expectations/upload-sample	Uploads a file and starts expectation + description tasks	↓ 🔒

Figure 29 DDM Swagger /expectations namespace

- The endpoints under **validations** namespace are developed for evaluating datasets against one or more stored expectation suites. They allow users to validate a single file across multiple suites or validate a collection of files against a single suite. The validation results can be retrieved using filtered queries or by ID for detailed inspection.

validations		Operations related to validations.	^
GET	/ddm/validations/results	Get all validation results with filters	↓ 🔒
POST	/ddm/validations/results	Save the result of an expectation suite validation on a dataset	↓ 🔒
GET	/ddm/validations/results/{result_id}	Get a detailed result entry	↓ 🔒
POST	/ddm/validations/validate/file-against-suites	Validate a single file against multiple expectation suites	↓ 🔒
POST	/ddm/validations/validate/files-against-suite	Validate multiple files against a single expectation suite	↓ 🔒

Figure 30 DDM Swagger /validations namespace

- The endpoints under **parametrics** are designed to support the frontend interface. They are developed to return available Great Expectations rules (categorized by data quality

dimensions such as uniqueness, completeness etc.) and expectation suite tuples (used to populate dropdowns in the frontend). Additionally, they return supported file types (both general and DataFrame-specific) to guide report and metadata compatibility.

Figure 31 DDM Swagger /parameters namespace

The Swagger documentation includes a comprehensive list of resource models that define the structure of both requests and responses across the API. These models, such as FileUpload, UploaderMetadataJSON, ExpectationSuite, and ValidationResult, standardize how clients should interact with the backend, ensuring clarity and consistency in data exchange. Each model encapsulates the necessary and optional fields required by its corresponding endpoint. The Appendix (Section 11) provides a link to the complete API documentation which maps each endpoint to its respective model and enumerates the expected arguments, types, and constraints, offering complete transparency for developers and integrators.

Figure 32 DDM Request/Response Models

7.3.3 Task Orchestration

The system relies on Celery for orchestrating background tasks. The message broker (PostgreSQL) queues jobs triggered by API requests. Celery workers, deployed in a distributed and scalable manner, “listen” for new tasks and execute them asynchronously. Tasks include parsing uploaded files, performing metadata inference, communicating with Zenoh storage peers, or interacting with smart contracts. The decoupled architecture ensures tasks can fail and retry independently of the main user flow. Celery enables concurrent, fault-tolerant processing across multiple compute nodes, ensuring efficient resource usage even under heavy loads.

7.3.4 Dataset Catalog

The PostgreSQL database acts as a dataset catalog and task result store. It stores structured metadata for each dataset, including schema, file paths, validation status, owner identifiers, and any blockchain-associated token IDs. Task progress, completion status, and logs are also maintained here. The catalog supports faceted search, filtering, and auditing of all data management operations.

The database schema is designed to support versioning, lineage tracking, and dynamic expansion with new metadata types, ensuring flexibility as ExtremeXP grows in scope and complexity.

7.3.5 Services

The service layer in the DDM system encapsulates the domain-specific functionalities that operate over ingested data assets. Each service is invoked asynchronously through the task orchestration layer, allowing for independent scaling and modular design. These services perform specialized operations on data assets and their metadata:

Ollama LLM Service: The Ollama LLM Service is a key component in the decentralized data management pipeline, responsible for intelligent metadata inference using large language models, specifically, *Mistral 7B (v3.7)*²⁴. This service is invoked by asynchronous celery tasks that parse uploaded files to generate human-readable descriptions and summaries. When users upload structured data files (CSVs, Excel spreadsheets, Parquet files, etc.), the DDM initiates a first task that automatically pulls out the schema and a second chained task that enriches this schema with helpful, column-level descriptions using the LLM service. A third chained task checks the file schema to suggest suitable stored expectation suites that match the dataset’s format and content. In addition, the Ollama service can be prompted dynamically with specific instructions per use-case.

Metadata Generation: When a file upload is complete, a background task uses this service to parse the contents of it and extract relevant metadata, including schema definitions, and statistical overviews. The **service** uses specialized libraries, depending on the file type. For example, Pandas²⁵ is used for DataFrame-compatible formats such as CSV, Excel, Parquet while GeoPandas²⁶ handles geospatial data, and image-specific libraries extract metadata from image formats like JPG, PNG etc. This approach ensures meaningful metadata extraction across datasets.

Dataset Report Generation: This module produces detailed, human-readable profiling reports that summarize the structure, quality, and statistical properties of a dataset. The resulting HTML

²⁴ <https://mistral.ai/news/announcing-mistral-7b>

²⁵ <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

²⁶ <https://geopandas.org/en/stable/>

reports are generated per file and stored for later retrieval, either through the catalog or API. These reports are essential for dataset quality assurance, dataset comparison, and curation. Crucially, they allow users to discover and assess the utility of a dataset without accessing the raw data itself, an essential capability for enabling NFT-backed provenance, controlled access, and fair reward attribution.

Expectation Suite Generation: Stakeholders can define expected properties that a dataset should satisfy across multiple data quality dimensions, such as uniqueness, validity, schema conformance, and numerical/statistical consistency. These expected properties provide an initial quality blueprint, ensuring datasets are reliable as well as semantically consistent.

Expectation Suite Validation: This service validates datasets against existing expectation suites that may have been defined by different users. It looks for issues like duplicate values, schema mismatches, invalid fields, or unusual numbers that do not align with the expected properties defined as rules in the expectation suites. The validation results can be logged, audited, and linked to data provenance records, offering accountability and trust across the ExtremeXP ecosystem.

Smart Contract Service: A dedicated service handles all smart contract operations—including compiling, deploying to the blockchain, and interacting with contracts after deployment. Solidity source code is compiled using the `pysolc-x`²⁷ Python library, which generates the ABI (Application Binary Interface), and bytecode needed to deploy contracts on EVM-compatible networks.

Compiled contracts are then deployed to the **Sepolia**²⁸ testnet. Deployment tasks are executed asynchronously using **Celery workers**, ensuring that blockchain operations do not block the main API thread and can be retried or monitored independently.

7.3.6 Smart Contracts

The implementation details of the smart contracts involved will be further explained as part of the deliverable D2.2- Final architecture, traceability, and trustworthiness for complex experiment-driven analytics.

7.3.7 Web3 Provider & Ethereum Virtual Machine

The role of this component is to ensure that every critical event, such as dataset submission, validation, or reward claim, is recorded immutably on-chain, supporting transparency and trustworthiness. On the frontend, users sign smart contract transactions through their MetaMask wallet, with the help of the **web3.js** library. At the backend, DDM uses **Web3.py** and Infura to handle contract transactions.

7.3.8 DDM Frontend

7.3.8.1 Overview

The user interface of the DDM is built as a multi-page React application. The frontend interacts with the backend through RESTful API calls, routed via NGINX, and communicates with the blockchain layer via injected Web3 provider ([MetaMask2024]). This enables seamless transactions with smart contracts, allowing for NFT minting, and decentralized provenance verification directly from the user interface.

The user interface is organized by the sidebar on the left which provides navigation across other DDM modules such as:

²⁷ <https://pypi.org/project/py-solc-x/>

²⁸ <https://sepolia.etherscan.io/>

- **Catalog** and **My Catalog** (for browsing assets),
- **Files, Chunks** and **Links** Uploads (for alternative ingestion methods),
- **Expectations** and **Validations** (for managing data quality),
- **Settings** and user profile controls.

Additionally, in the footer of the sidebar, users can find quick-access buttons that enhance usability: one for connecting a Web3 wallet, another for toggling between light and dark themes, and a logoff button.

Figure 33 Frontend Page - File Uploads

7.3.8.2 Files/Links/Chunks Upload Pages

The above figure represents the **Upload Files and Metadata** interface within the ExtremeXP DDM (Decentralized Data Management) system. It allows users to stage multiple files for upload into a specified project directory, in this case, test_project1/subfolder1. Each file listed includes:

- **File name and icon:** Indicating the type of file (e.g., .json, .pdf, .csv, .geojson) with a relevant icon for easy visual identification.
- **Use Case field:** A chips text field where users can assign the file to specific use cases or categories.
- **Description field:** Allows users to provide a description of the file being uploaded.
- **Metadata link:** Opens an interface for entering or editing metadata (as a JSON object or a JSON file) manually or automatically before uploading.
- **Status indicator:** Displays the real-time state of each file within the upload pipeline. Initial states such as ” etc.)

- **Expansion (+) icon:** Reveals additional details and post-processing outputs associated with that specific file. Specifically, when the Dataset Report Generation task finishes (triggered by the backend), the profile report is made accessible here, as shown in the next figure.

Figure 34 Frontend Page - Report Generation on File Upload

The behavior and structure are consistent across other upload pages, such as Upload Links and Chunked Uploads offering a unified and intuitive user experience across upload mechanisms.

7.3.8.3 Catalog/ MyCatalog Pages

The figure below showcases the **Catalog View** of the ExtremeXP DDM system, a core interface that allows users to explore and manage uploaded datasets. This view provides advanced controls for filtering, sorting, and interacting with files stored across the decentralized infrastructure. Users can refine their search using a variety of input fields positioned at the top of the catalog. These include:

- **Filenames:** Filter by partial or exact matches on multiple values
- **Project ID** and **Parent Files:** Restrict results to specific logical groupings or project paths.
- **Use Cases** and **User IDs:** Select context-specific tags or uploader identities.
- **Date Range (From/To):** Enables temporal filtering based on upload timestamps.
- **File Type Dropdown:** Offers multi-select filtering across various file formats (e.g., CSV, Excel, JSON, PNG).
- **Min/Max File Size:** Helps narrow results by file size boundaries (in bytes).

The screenshot shows the 'Catalog' page in the DDM system. It features a sidebar with navigation options like 'Explore', 'My Catalog', 'Projects', 'Upload', 'Files', 'Chunks', 'Links', 'Expectations', 'Suites', 'Create', 'Validations', 'Results', 'Policies', and 'Settings'. The main area contains a search and filter interface with fields for 'File Names', 'Project ID', 'Use Cases', 'From Date', 'To Date', 'File Types', 'User IDs', 'Parent Files', 'Min File Size', and 'Max File Size'. Below this is a table of file assets.

Selection	Filename	Project Path	Use Cases	Created	File Type	File Size	User	Pa	File	Actions
<input type="checkbox"/>	CSV (Comma-separated values)	project		Jun 12, 2025, 01:26 AM	json	169 KB	orestis	Nc	rel	file ov
<input type="checkbox"/>	Excel (XLSX)									
<input type="checkbox"/>	Excel (XLS)									
<input type="checkbox"/>	test_project1/subfolder1	test_project1/subfolder1		Jun 12, 2025, 01:25 AM	pdf	387 KB	orestis	Nc	rel	file ov
<input type="checkbox"/>	oslo_ddm.drawio.png	test_project1/subfolder1	AMBUS	Jun 12, 2025, 01:25 AM	png	547 KB	orestis	Nc	rel	file ov
<input type="checkbox"/>	titanic (3).json	test_project1/subfolder1	IDEKO	Jun 12, 2025, 01:25 AM	json	61 KB	orestis	Nc	rel	file ov
<input type="checkbox"/>	titanic.json	ZZZZ		Jun 6, 2025, 12:36 AM	json	169 KB	orestis	Nc	rel	file ov

Figure 35 Frontend Page - Catalog

Each row of the table represents a file asset, displaying:

- **Selection Checkbox:** For bulk operations (download, delete)
- **Filename and Project Path:** Including the full folder structure.
- **Use Cases:** Rendered as colored chips/tags
- **Creation Date, File Type, Size, and Uploader** metadata.
- **Action Icons:** Offer quick access to:
 - View uploader and file metadata
 - Preview or download the file
 - View Report if available
 - Trigger validations against many expectations suites
 - View Validations Results
 - Delete the entry

The "My Catalog" view in the ExtremeXP DDM system provides personalized insights and controls for the datasets uploaded by the currently logged-in user. This includes access to file history logs (tracking metadata generation, profile report creation, and upload events), NFT-related metadata, access control settings, and detailed usage statistics such as download patterns over time and by IP address. These additional features allow users to monitor the lifecycle and impact of their data assets more transparently and effectively, as presented in the next figures.

Figure 36 Frontend Page - MyCatalog

Figure 37 Frontend Page - MyCatalog Logs

7.3.8.4 Expectations/Validations Pages

The "Define Expectations" interface shown in Figure 38 is part of the guided workflow for creating an Expectation Suite within the ExtremeXP DDM platform. After uploading a sample file, users are presented with an automatically populated interface where column names, types, and descriptions (derived from an earlier completed task powered by LLM analysis) are prefilled to assist in defining validation rules. The interface is divided into table-level and column-level expectations, allowing users to configure constraints such as expected row counts or data types. Each column entry includes editable descriptions and selectable rules, combining automated insight with human-in-the-loop refinement to ensure the dataset meets quality and schema standards before validation or reward eligibility.

1 [Create Expectation Suite](#)
2 [Upload Sample File](#)
3 [Define Expectations](#)
4 [Finalize](#)

Table-Level Expectations

schema

expect_table_column_count_to_be_between

max_value: min_value:

expect_table_column_count_to_equal

value:

expect_table_columns_to_match_ordered_list

expect_table_columns_to_match_set

volume

expect_table_row_count_to_be_between

max_value: min_value: strict_max: strict_min:

expect_table_row_count_to_equal

value:

expect_table_row_count_to_equal_other_table

Column-Level Expectations

Column Name	Column Description	Validation Rules
accuracy	Estimated accuracy of the GPS coordinates in meters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> expect_column_to_exist <input type="checkbox"/> column: <input type="text" value="accuracy"/> column index: <input type="text" value="7"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> expect_column_values_to_be_of_type <input type="checkbox"/> mostly: <input type="text" value="0.95"/> type: <input type="text" value="float"/> <input type="checkbox"/> expect_column_values_to_be_in_type_list <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> expect_column_values_to_match_json_schema <input type="checkbox"/>
confidence	Confidence level of the detected activity	<input type="checkbox"/> expect_column_to_exist <input type="checkbox"/> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> expect_column_values_to_be_of_type <input type="checkbox"/> mostly: <input type="text"/> type: <input type="text"/>

Figure 38 Frontend Page - Create Expectations

In the final step of the workflow, users can review the expectation suite and, if desired, register a dataset request on-chain—linking the defined rules with future dataset validations and reward claims, as presented in Figure 39.

Table Expectations

Filter by Table Category:

Expectation ID	Category ID	Arguments
expect_table_column_count_to_be_between	schema	max_value: 100, min_value: 6
expect_table_column_count_to_equal	schema	value: 100
expect_table_row_count_to_be_between	volume	max_value: 1000, min_value: 10, strict_max: false, strict_min: false
expect_table_row_count_to_equal	volume	value: 50

Column Expectations

Filter by Column: | Filter by Column Category:

Expectation ID	Category ID	Column ID	Arguments
expect_column_to_exist	schema	accuracy	column_index: 7
expect_column_values_to_be_of_type	schema	localised	type: float, mostly: 0.95

Figure 39 Frontend Page - View Expectations

Finally, when a user uploads a dataset and selects an expectation suite to validate it against, the system automatically generates a visual validation report (Figure 40). This report offers clear and interactive visualizations—including bar charts, tables, and radar plots—that highlight which

expectations were met or failed. It provides both high-level overviews (e.g., table-level schema or volume checks) and granular, column-level diagnostics, enabling users to quickly interpret data quality, identify issues, and confirm whether the dataset meets the defined standards for acceptance or reward.

Figure 40 Frontend Page - Validate File against Expectations

8 Experiment Cards

8.1 Scope

As part of ExtremeXP’s goal to support large-scale, trustworthy AI experimentation, it is essential to document experiments in a way that is transparent, and easy to understand and share among collaborators or involved stakeholders. Moreover, reusing knowledge acquired from the experimentation process becomes increasingly necessary. To meet these needs, we introduce the Experiment Cards framework, a lightweight and structured module to capture and present/showcase key information about each experiment, focusing on both quantitative and qualitative aspects. These cards include important details, such as the experiment’s intent, methods used, evaluation results, and user feedback, among others. They help ensure that it becomes easier to document experiments, review or compare them, and reproduce them across teams and use cases. Thus, Experiment Cards play an important role in supporting ExtremeXP’s broader objectives: encouraging human oversight and enabling collaboration and learning from past experiments.

As part of this deliverable, we describe the approach we followed in the design and implementation of the Experiment Cards component within the project.

8.2 Approach

A responsible and trustworthy approach to documenting AI experimentation and preserving the knowledge acquired and lessons learnt should support transparency, accountability, and reproducibility at all stages of the development pipeline. This includes capturing both technical details—such as data sources, preprocessing steps, model settings, and evaluation metrics—as well as qualitative aspects, including user feedback and fairness considerations. The Experiment Cards framework builds upon existing best practices in trustworthy AI documentation (e.g., Model Cards [DEP+23], [CDV+22], [M19], [D23], [BPL+23] and Datasheets for Datasets [G18], [P23], [B21]). It combines structured manual documentation with automation features. Subsequently, Experiment Cards aim to be integrated into the process of experimentation within ExtremeXP and are thus designed to be updated at key points in the experimentation lifecycle, including setup and configuration phase, following any alteration or addition of new metadata or pertinent (to the experiment) information and after model training and evaluation.

So far, two modules/interfaces have been developed to support this process:

- a manual input form, which allows users to contribute structured data and free-text insights, lessons learnt and recommendations, and
- an automated component that extracts metadata from the experiment environment and pre-fills card fields.

The process of the development of the Experiment Cards component, illustrated in Figure 41, began with a comprehensive review and analysis of existing card-based frameworks, including Croissant for datasets²⁹, Hugging Face’s annotated model cards³⁰, use case cards [HFB+24], and system cards [G24], [GK22], [Meta24], [Go24] formats. This review ensured the reuse and adaptation of established practices, while identifying gaps specific to experiment tracking and

²⁹ <https://research.google/blog/croissant-a-metadata-format-for-ml-ready-datasets/>

³⁰ <https://huggingface.co/docs/hub/model-cards>

knowledge maintenance. After this comprehensive review, core metadata and documentation attributes were defined to reflect the needs of experimentation workflows within the project and across all use cases, where an iterative process has been followed. These attributes include technical information such as algorithms, parameters, and datasets; workflow metadata including experiment status and steps; analytical context such as intent and evaluation strategy; and collaborative or qualitative dimensions including contributors, lessons learnt, and user feedback, for instance regarding the experiment execution, performance, or configuration decisions.

The defined attributes were afterwards reviewed, documented, and categorized. A detailed [Experiment Card Template](#), developed as a spreadsheet, formalizes the structure of these attributes. The template specifies each attribute's mapped name with existing frameworks, description, hierarchical grouping, lifecycle phase, data type, source (manual or automated), and respective ExtremeXP component, whose output could serve as an input to the automatic prefilling of the experiment details (whenever available). It also identifies whether the attribute is mandatory and enumerates any vocabularies or external references, serving also as a validation tool for implementation.

The next step included the backend and API development. Specifically, the implementation includes the development of APIs, which correspond to lifecycle events, such as experiment creation, modification, and completion. To support human-in-the-loop interaction, a form-based interface was developed, combining structured input fields with free-text areas. This allows users to contribute with their feedback, attach supporting materials, record evaluation scores, and reflect on the outcomes of the experiment but also on each instantiation/run.

Finally, experiment cards are made accessible through a dedicated frontend interface (as described in Section 8.4 and illustrated in Figure 41). Users can filter, search, and compare cards based on attributes such as intent, algorithm, dataset, or model used.

Figure 41 Design and implementation process of Experiment Cards

8.3 Conceptual and Technical Architecture

Figure 42 presents the main pillars and key attributes of the Experiment Cards framework. This conceptual model captures essential elements of experimentation, offering a standardized and extensible way to document, communicate, and reuse experiment metadata, configuration, and lessons learned. The technical architecture of the Experiment Cards framework, shown in Figure 43, designed to support the dynamic, lifecycle-aware documentation of experimentation processes, follows a modular structure across four tiers: the Human-in-the-Loop Layer, the Logic Layer, the Pre-processing Layer, and the Data Layer.

At the top, the Human-in-the-Loop Layer offers user-facing functionalities, including forms for data input, a centralized page for experiment visualization, individual forms, serving as the “cards” for each experiment, and search tools for retrieving experiments based on user queries. The Logic Layer manages core backend operations; it monitors experiment status, triggers updates, handles data synchronization, and enables advanced querying. It serves as the central subcomponent, connecting user interfaces with the data processing layers. The Pre-processing Layer handles the extraction, cleaning, and transformation of data. This ensures that both raw and processed outputs are prepared and aligned with the defined documentation schema. As a result, many card fields can be automatically filled without manual insertion from the Data Abstraction Layer (DAL), improving consistency and reducing users’ effort. The Data Layer is responsible for persisting all documentation and captured knowledge. Information is stored in JSON format for both human readability and machine parsing and managed using a PostgreSQL database to ensure long-term accessibility and query performance.

Figure 42 Pillars and Core Attributes of Experiment Cards.

Figure 43 Technical Architecture of the Experiment Cards Framework.

8.4 APIs and User Interfaces

The Experiment Cards framework is designed for seamless integration into experimentation environments and the ExtremeXP framework. User-generated content—such as lessons learnt, evaluations, and recommendations—is entered manually through web-based forms or submitted via RESTful API endpoints, using POST and PUT requests. In parallel, technical metadata is automatically collected from the DAL and added to the card without requiring user intervention. This approach ensures that documentation is logged consistently throughout the experimentation lifecycle without manual burdens.

The backend is implemented in Python, with Flask providing the API layer. All experiment data is stored in JSON format, which supports both flexibility and structured access. To ensure reliable deployment across environments, the system is fully containerized using Docker, allowing for easy scaling and portability between development and production setups. The system's API documentation via Swagger (Figure 44 and also Appendix in Section 11), allows developers to programmatically submit or retrieve card data.

Figure 44 Screenshot of the Swagger interface showing Experiment Cards API endpoints for experiment metadata and lessons learnt.

To facilitate human-in-the-loop knowledge capture, the Experiment Cards component provides structured and user-friendly interfaces to simplify the documentation process. An example of such interfaces is the form-based feedback page, used to collect user input directly after an experiment execution (see Figure 45). This form allows users to share qualitative insights through the *Lessons Learnt* field, documenting recommendations, and feedback on challenges and outcomes. Users can also rate the experiment (Experiment Rating) and score individual runs (Run Ratings) on a Likert scale from 1 to 7. In addition, the form supports uploading supplementary material—such as evaluation results or related scientific works—in various formats. This ensures that both qualitative and quantitative feedback are linked to each experiment.

In addition, a centralized page provides access to all documented Experiment Cards (see Figure 46), allowing users to browse, filter, and search experiments by attributes such as intent, algorithm, dataset, or model and thus enabling them to compare results, retrieve past configurations, and build on previous knowledge. Lastly, an individual modal for each experiment card (which could also be served as a page) is provided to the ExtremeXP users for them to view in a user-friendly and comprehensive manner the most important features of each conducted experiment (Figure 47).

Submit Lessons Learnt for experiment with id jZa-mJQBZTyxy1ACX1W8

Please fill out the form below to submit your feedback regarding the execution of the experiment.

Lessons Learnt: Cover topics such as what went well, limitations, advantages, conclusions, and any other relevant observations.

Experiment Rating: Provide a number between 1 and 7, where 1 is the lowest and 7 is the highest.

Run Ratings: Enter a comma-separated list of numbers between 1 and 7, corresponding to the runs of the experiment.

Additional Documentation: If you have any additional documentation or files to share, please attach them using the file upload option below.

Lessons Learnt:

Experiment Rating (1-7):

Run Ratings (1-7, comma separated):

Attach PDF File:

Choose file No file chosen

Submit

Figure 45 Form-based interface for submitting post-experiment feedback and lessons learned.

Query Experiments

Experiment Name: Intent: Start Date:

End Date: Algorithm: Metric Name:

Experiment ID	Experiment Name	Start Date	End Date	Intent	Lessons Learnt	Dataset	User Rating	Collaborators	Status	Experiment Cards	More Details
exp_1	Experiment_1	2025-01-02 10:00:00	2025-01-02 11:15:00	Regression	Lessons Learnt 1 text	MOBI2	★★★★☆	User_B	completed	View Details	View Details
exp_10	Experiment_10	2025-01-01 08:00:00	2025-01-01 09:00:00	Regression	Lessons Learnt 10 text	ManufacturingDataset	★★★★☆	User_A	completed	View Details	View Details
exp_11	Experiment_11	2025-01-02 10:00:00	2025-01-02 11:15:00	Classification	Lessons Learnt 11 text	AirbusDataset	★★★★☆	User_B	completed	View Details	View Details
exp_12	Experiment_12	2025-01-03 14:00:00	2025-01-03 15:30:00	Classification	Lessons Learnt 12 text	MOBI	★★★☆☆	User_C	completed	View Details	View Details
exp_13	Experiment_13	2025-01-04 09:30:00	2025-01-04 10:45:00	Regression	Lessons Learnt 13 text	MOBI2	★★★★☆	User_D	completed	View Details	View Details
exp_14	Experiment_14	2025-01-05 13:00:00	2025-01-05 14:00:00	Classification	Lessons Learnt 14 text	ManufacturingDataset	★★★★☆	User_E	completed	View Details	View Details

Figure 46 Central Experiment Page View.

Experiment Card for moby-exp1

General Information

- Experiment Name: moby-exp1
- Experiment ID: f-T155IBLOWBshllLyl
- Start Date: 2025-01-01 08:00:00
- End Date: 2025-01-01 09:00:00
- Status: completed
- Collaborators: Georgia Gkioka, Yiannis Vergrnadis
- Constraints:
 - ID: ConstrainDX, On: SVM, Is Hard: Yes, How: Use
- User Interaction: None

Intent

- Intent: Classification

Requirements

- Metrics: Accuracy, Method: CrossValidation, Objective: Maximize

Variability Points

Models

- Algorithm: SVM
- Parameter: C
- Parameter Values: 0.1, 0.01, 1

Datasets

- Dataset Name: InputCSV
- Dataset Path: "MOBY/datasets/testcase_locations_sample.csv"
- Zenoh Key: example_key
- Reviewer Score: 78

Processing

- Workflow ID: f-T155IBLOWBshllMSu5
- Tasks:
 - ReadData
 - PreprocessData
 - TimeBasedClustering
 - TimeAndSpeedBasedClustering
 - RuleBasedSegmentCombination
 - ModeEstimation
 - RuleBasedSegmentationCombinationUsingModes
 - ActivityEstimation

Lessons Learnt

- Lessons: The experiment went well.
- Experiment Rating: 7
- Run Ratings: [6, Null, 2]
- Best Performing Run: 1

Evaluation

- Metrics: Ml_Accuracy, Ml_Recall
- Run Metrics: [0.67, 0.65], [0.5, 0.6], [0.47, 0.62]

Figure 47 Individual Experiment Card View.

9 Conclusion

This deliverable describes the final version of the eight core components of the ExtremeXP framework listed in Table 1, and the corresponding tools and services. This list includes both components developed in the first half of the project (whose intermediate status had been described in D5.2 [KGR+24]), and components developed entirely in the second half of the project (e.g., Experiment Cards).

The main achievements of the work in WP5 can be summarized in the following:

- Design, development, and testing of **tools for specifying workflows and experiments** conforming to the ExtremeXP Domain Specific Language (DSL). These user-facing tools are both textual (DSL framework and associated editors) and graphical (Graphical Workflow Editor and Experiment Designer). Whichever combination of tools users choose, the final results are experiment (and associated workflow) specifications described in the ExtremeXP DSL, that can be used as input to the Experimentation Engine (ExpEngine).
- Design, development, and testing of the **ExpEngine**, capable of parsing experiment specifications outlined in the DSL, scheduling workflows for execution in the chosen executionware, and saving workflows parameters and results using the APIs of the Data Abstraction Layer (DAL) and the Decentralized Data Management (DDM) services. The ExpEngine can be used either as a Python module or as a service.
- Iterative design, development and testing of **DAL**, aiming at providing full traceability and repeatability of experiments run in the ExtremeXP framework and centralizing access to the data generated via experiments in ExtremeXP.
- Analysis of requirements, design, and implementation of extensions to the **executionware** of the ExtremeXP framework (Proactive Python DSK) in the direction of supporting resource monitoring, interacting with running jobs, and deployment based on Docker and Python virtual environments.
- Iterative design, development, and testing of **DDM**, a complete solution for handling datasets and their associated metadata in the ExtremeXP framework. These datasets are either inputs or outputs of experiments.
- Design, development, and testing of the blockchain-based attribute-based **access control** (ABAC) approach of the ExtremeXP framework, offering modular, dynamic, and decentralized access control to all the services within the ExtremeXP framework.
- Design and implementation of the **Experiments Cards** component, aiming at enabling the reuse of knowledge gained from the ExtremeXP experiments between different stakeholders.

These achievements have produced the following results in reference to the target WP5 KPIs:

- KPI-1.1: Meta-models and language specification for experiment-driven analytics covering 100% of the ExtremeXP use cases' needs.
 - The final version of the DSLs allows modeling all the aspects pertinent to experimentation of complex analytics workflows (workflows, experiments, spaces).
 - We have used it in all five use cases of ExtremeXP.
- KPI-6.1: Develop a minimum of 3 context handlers for each use case.
 - 3 context handlers are already defined in the smart contract, experimenting with them, for rules 1, 2, 3, 4 and 15 of Table 3. Further development will be completed and reported on D2.2.
- KPI-6.2: Publish access policy model including at least 3 detailed policies for each use case
 - 15 policy rules have been defined across all use cases (Table 3).

- KPI-4.1 Running at least 10 different experiments in each ExtremeXP use case using the ExtremeXP framework.
 - Each use case has specified and run several (more than 10) experiments using the Experimentation Engine and the rest of the WP5 components.

The described core components delivered by WP5 have already been integrated into the ExtremeXP framework and used by the use case partners to design and execute experiments in an intuitive, secure, and reproducible way. The integration efforts and final version of the ExtremeXP framework will be detailed in M33 as part of D6.2, while the use case pilot demonstrations and validation will be delivered in M36 as part of D6.3.

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11 Appendix

In this Appendix we provide the Swagger specification of four main services of the ExtremeXP framework: ExpEngine (Section 2), DAL (Section 3), DDM (Section 7), Experiment Cards (Section 8). Their integration will be detailed in the next deliverable of WP6, i.e., D6.2.

Table 4: Links for Swagger/OpenAPI specifications of four ExtremeXP core services.

ExpEngine	YAML	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-experimentation-engine-docs/blob/main/openapi.yaml
	HTML	https://extremexp-horizon.github.io/extremexp-experimentation-engine-docs
DAL	YAML	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremexp-dal/blob/main/openapi.yaml
	HTML	https://extremexp-horizon.github.io/extremexp-dal
DDM	YAML	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/DDM/blob/main/openapi.yaml
	HTML	https://extremexp-horizon.github.io/DDM/
Experiment Cards	YAML	https://github.com/extremexp-HORIZON/extremeXP_experimentCards/blob/main/static/swagger.yaml
	HTML	https://extremexp-horizon.github.io/extremeXP_experimentCards